

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

The Digital Democracy Lab Handbook

Lessons from an experimental
AI-supported deliberative process with
practical guidance for facilitators,
public servants, and civic technologists

January 2026

DOI Number [10.5281/zenodo.18374697](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18374697)

Funded by
the European Union

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Project Information

This handbook was developed within the framework of the **Knowledge Technologies for Democracy (KT4D)** project.

Grant Agreement No.: 101094302 — KT4D

Funding programme: Horizon Europe

Granting authority: European Research Executive Agency (REA)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094302.

Acknowledgements

This handbook was developed as part of the Knowledge Technologies for Democracy (KT4D) project, with the support of our consortium partners across Europe. We are especially grateful to our Work Package partner, **Hybridcore**, whose collaboration in the development of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator was essential to the work presented here.

EU Funding & Disclaimer

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Digital Democracy Lab Handbook

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1 Preface:

This is a handbook to help you find effective ways
–perhaps *your own ways*–
of working with emerging technology

A little guidance and encouragement regarding how this handbook is intended to help, and for whom it has been written.

I. Who is this for?

This handbook is primarily designed to equip and encourage democratic practitioners and facilitators to ask meaningful questions and make informed decisions about technology, in pursuit of more effective and democratically grounded processes. It is also intended for public servants in local, regional, or national administrations who are exploring or planning democratic exchange processes using digital or AI-informed technologies and civic-oriented technologists eager to explore how tools like AI could be made fit-for-purpose for democratic purposes and in democratic contexts. The handbook can support each of these groups in planning these processes, drafting tenders for technical support, or developing design specifications.

II. In order to do what?

Each section of this handbook is designed to enhance your ability to critically and constructively navigate the increasingly intersecting fields of emerging technologies and democratic exchange – most specifically, the challenges of effectively integrating AI into deliberative processes.

In writing this, we are anticipating that you have some – or a depth of – knowledge and experience designing and facilitating analogue democratic exchange processes - mini-publics, participatory budgets, co-creative processes, etc. - and, thus, are fairly confident and knowledgeable regarding the language, values, principles, and models of democracy and democratic exchange processes.

That said, we are also anticipating that the readers of this handbook may have vastly different experiences with—and preferences for—the use of technologies and AI specifically. You may have a wide-ranging knowledge, experience, and, what is called, critical digital literacy, i.e., the skills, competencies, and analytical viewpoints that allows a person to constructively use, understand, and create digital media and tools with awareness of the risks and mediating factors to bare in mind. Alternatively, you may, humbly, acknowledge you have zero critical digital literacy or understanding of how digital platforms operate. Both of these positions are appropriate and useful starting places to engage with this handbook.

Our goal, regardless of where you're at with technology right now, is to offer you a way forward to build—or further develop—your critical digital literacy, in complement with your democratic expertise, in order to enhance:

- (1) Your critical understanding of the roles and impacts AI can have when integrated into democratic exchange processes - generally and in unique contexts with particular AI tools; and
- (2) Your practical ability to act constructively when navigating opportunities to integrate AI into democratic exchange processes,
 - (a) For example, this handbook and its associated assets offer guidance for how to effectively:
 - (i) Navigate conversations about and requests for the use of certain AI tools in specific democratic exchange processes with constructive criticality;
 - (ii) Discern the risks and value-adds of the AI tool in a specific setting and process, including asking questions related to what the AI would substitute, what the AI would add/complement, and what the AI would remove from the process, with consideration for the meaningful efficiencies added and meaningful inefficiencies lost; and
 - (iii) Design and facilitate impactful democratic exchange processes that meaningfully integrate AI.

III. Some thoughts on how to use this Handbook

1. This handbook does not contain instructions for replicating exact democratic exchanges or experiences.
2. Each democratic experience is a function of its context, so you will almost certainly need to adjust elements of what you are designing / facilitating to feel right for you and the people, place, and technology you are working with.
3. The goal isn't perfection, in fact, such a pursuit can reinforce a form of process rigidity that reduces your ability to adapt to the dynamic nature of genuine democratic exchange; Plan, Engage, Observe, Adapt as Needed, Reflect, and Iterate.
4. It's not about using whichever technology is "best"; it's about being able to discern which technology, if any, can enhance the efficacy of democratic exchange in your context.
5. The most important thing to learn: How to ask critical and constructive questions

*The most effective way to navigate AI integration in democratic settings is through **critical inquiry rather than following predetermined rules**. Questions serve multiple crucial functions in this work. They help you assess whether AI proposals genuinely serve democratic purposes or merely apply efficiency logic to democratic contexts. They guide your design decisions when you do integrate AI, ensuring choices remain grounded in democratic goods rather than technological capability.*

They provide frameworks for facilitation, helping you transform technological interactions into opportunities for democratic learning and critical engagement.

For this reason, the questions embedded throughout each section should not be seen as rhetorical—they're practical tools you should return to repeatedly as circumstances evolve, contexts shift, and new challenges emerge. Some questions help you evaluate specific proposals ("What democratic capacities would this AI add, replace, or eliminate entirely?"). Others guide ongoing process decisions ("Where does this process benefit from friction rather than seamlessness?"). Still others support facilitation in real-time ("How can I turn this technical glitch into a democratic learning opportunity?"). By centring questions rather than answers, we aim to build your capacity for independent critical judgment about AI's role in democratic exchange—a capacity that will serve you far better than any checklist or protocol as technologies and contexts continue to evolve.

IV. The Origins of this Handbook's Insights

This handbook emerges from three years of research, design, experimentation, and critical analysis conducted as part of the Knowledge Technologies for Democracy (KT4D) project, an EU-funded initiative

exploring the intersection of AI, big data, and democratic governance. Rather than pursuing technological fixes, KT4D placed cultural values and identity at the centre of its approach, examining both AI's potential to enhance civic participation and its risks of fostering anti-democratic environments. Within this context, we designed and developed the [Digital Democracy Lab \(DDL\)](#)—an experimental deliberative process—and the [Digital Democracy Demonstrator \(DDD\)](#)—a purpose-built AI platform designed to be transparent, contestable, and critically examinable rather than seamlessly efficient.

Between 2024 and 2025, we deployed the Lab and Demonstrator across four distinct contexts: with policymakers in Brussels, citizens in Madrid and Krakow, and technology professionals in Dublin. Each workshop revealed how the same AI system functioned differently across cultural and institutional contexts, how participants valued opportunities to critique rather than simply use AI, and how deliberate imperfections often proved more democratically valuable than polished performance. The insights, recipes, and practical guidance in this handbook are grounded in these real-world experiments; their successes, failures, compromises, and unexpected discoveries about what AI can and cannot contribute to democratic exchange.

V. How we've formatted this Handbook

At the onset, it should be noted that this handbook is loosely structured to resemble something closer to a cookbook than a comprehensive manual. The thinking here is that technologies, like AI, and the contexts in which they are used and could be useful (or harmful) are constantly shifting and evolving. Similar to teaching someone how to cook, our intention is to equip you with the confidence, criticality, questions, and ways of continuing to learn so that you can evaluate, adapt, and execute constructive and effective technologically infused democratic exchanges, no matter your context or “ingredients.”

With this handbook you can pick and choose which elements—*recipes*—you want to engage with and when. These decisions could be based on where you actually are in a process of integrating AI into a democratic exchange process. Alternatively, you might choose to explore a certain topic at your own leisure based on general interest or curiosity you might have. On the other hand altogether, you can read this handbook from front to back as an overarching introduction and guiding tool for your future or ongoing work with technology and democracy.

Regardless, we are hopeful that by offering you a vision of when and how certain skills, questions, and models might be most relevant within the whole journey of potentially integrating AI into your democratic exchange, you can be empowered to incorporate and expand upon each offer at the moments when they are most relevant.

2 Get Ready:

Understand the Context and Potentials of AI with Democratic Exchange

Some (hopefully useful) insights into the context and potentials of AI embedded democratic exchange.

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Understanding the current moment in which AI and democracy intersect is essential for making thoughtful decisions about technological integration in democratic processes. This isn't just about learning new tools—it's about recognizing the broader forces shaping how AI gets introduced into democratic settings and understanding both its genuine potential and its real risks.

The Context: The Efficiency Imperative

I. Why AI Keeps Showing Up in Democratic Settings

We live in an era defined by what we might call the "optimization imperative"; a pervasive assumption that making things faster, smoother, and more efficient represents inherent progress. This mindset has migrated from commercial and industrial contexts into virtually every domain, including democratic governance, often without critical examination of whether efficiency actually serves democratic purposes.

The rise of this efficiency paradigm directly correlates with the growing influence of technologists and software engineers, not just in Silicon Valley but increasingly within governmental institutions and democratic organizations. Their optimization mindset has become a dominant framework through which we evaluate democratic systems themselves.

This creates a fundamental misalignment. *Democratic processes* are intentionally designed with what appear to be inefficiencies: separation of powers, checks and balances, extended deliberation periods, multiple rounds of review, protest. **These aren't design flaws to be optimized away**; they are essential features that prevent hasty decisions, create space for diverse perspectives, and enable the kind of slow, careful collective sense-making that effective democratic exchange requires.

Yet we increasingly see democratic processes subjected to the same efficiency metrics that govern technological development, with calls to "streamline" decision-making, "automate" participation, and create "frictionless" civic engagement. The language itself reveals the problem. When we apply commercial optimization logic to democratic processes, we risk optimizing away the very characteristics that make democracy work.

II. Government is Not a Business; Democracy is not a Transaction

The mantra that "government should run like a business" has shaped public expectations and administrative practices for decades. This business-thinking substitutes concepts central to democratic governance.

"Customers" replace citizens, "efficiency" trumps deliberation, and "streamlined service delivery" takes precedence over meaningful participation in collective decision-making.

While this thinking can improve certain institutional and administrative functions, it becomes problematic when applied to democratic exchange processes. Democracy is not a transaction; it is not a service delivery mechanism. It is a complex system for inquiry, imagination, contestation, and collective decision-making that necessarily involves disagreement, uncertainty, and the kind of messiness that business optimization seeks to eliminate.

AI accelerates this trend by making optimization appear not just preferable but inevitable. When technological solutions promise to make democratic processes faster and smoother, questioning these improvements can feel like standing in the way of progress. But this "progress" rhetoric obscures a crucial question: progress toward what? If the goal is more *efficient* democracy, AI may deliver. If the goal is more *effective* democracy – democracy that strengthens civic capacity, builds trust, enables meaningful participation, and enhances collective solidarity – the relationship becomes far more complex.

III. The Current Wave of AI Proposals in Democratic Settings

Democratic practitioners increasingly face proposals to incorporate AI into their work, often wrapped in appealing language about innovation and efficiency. These proposals rarely emerge from identified democratic challenges; instead, they typically represent available technological solutions searching for applications.

Consider the pattern: technologists develop tools optimized for commercial contexts (customer service bots, data analytics, automated content generation), then propose applying these tools to democratic settings with minimal adaptation. The assumption is that what works for managing consumer interactions will naturally improve citizen engagement, that tools designed for individual users will enhance collective decision-making, and that systems optimized for speed and convenience will strengthen deliberative depth.

This approach fundamentally misunderstands how democratic exchange functions. Democratic processes require different success criteria than commercial ones: meaningful disagreement rather than satisfied customers, collective agency rather than individual convenience, thoughtful deliberation rather than rapid transactions.

IV. Real Examples from Democratic Practice

Two current examples illuminate both the appeal and the problems of applying AI to democratic processes:

1. [The Habermas Machine](#) represents the most sophisticated attempt to scale deliberative democracy through AI. This system, trained as a large language model, mediates human deliberation by taking participants' personal opinions and critiques, then generating and refining statements to express common ground among the group. The promise is compelling: dramatically scaling participation.

However, the system's design reveals the optimization logic at work. By continuously seeking common ground and generating consensus statements, it smooths over the productive

disagreement that enables participants to understand complex trade-offs and conflicting interests. The "least common denominator" approach may produce efficient consensus, but it eliminates the friction that helps people develop more sophisticated positions through encountering different perspectives. What appears as democratic scaling may actually hollow out the deliberative substance.

2. [The Cascais Participatory Budget](#) takes a different approach, using AI to support citizen proposal-writing and administrative filtering. Citizens can access an AI assistant trained on successful past proposals to help improve their submissions, particularly valuable for those with language barriers or limited writing confidence. Simultaneously, AI filters submissions for eligibility, reducing the administrative burden on public servants.

This appears more benign – supporting participation rather than mediating it – but subtle trade-offs emerge. When AI helps citizens write "better" proposals, whose definition of "better" prevails? Research shows people tend to accept AI-generated text uncritically – and potentially apathetically – because it sounds authoritative, raising questions about whether citizens' actual voices remain present in the "improved" proposals. Furthermore, in accepting plausible algorithm-generated proposals, not only are citizens being invited to avoid opportunities for genuine enactment of their democratic capabilities and faculties, but also, dangerously, allowing their confidence in such democratic capabilities and faculties to be degrading by leaning into an apathetic assumption that the machine seemingly does it better, so by correlation, citizens must do it worse. Beyond this, the current manual process of reviewing thousands of proposals, while resource-intensive, allows public servants to read between the lines; to understand community concerns, identify systemic issues, and recognize patterns of need that don't fit standard categories. AI filtering gains efficiency while potentially losing this valuable interpretive dimension.

Both examples show AI being deployed to address genuine democratic challenges: scale in the first case, accessibility and administrative burden in the second. But both also demonstrate how efficiency-focused solutions can inadvertently undermine the democratic depth they're meant to serve.

The responsibility thus falls on the practitioners designing and facilitating democratic processes – the individuals who must navigate the requests, demands, and opportunities to integrate AI – to make critical and democratically constructive choices about the technology they integrate into their processes. This necessitates a deep understanding of the potential that technologies, like AI, carry as they relate to enhancing – or diminishing – the effectiveness of the democratic processes they aim to enact. The next section will offer some insight into the criteria and considerations one might weigh while considering such a decision.

The Potentials: Distinguishing Efficiency from Efficacy

I. Why the Distinction Matters

The central question for democratic practitioners isn't whether AI can make a process more efficient; it generally can. The question of significance is whether that efficiency serves or undermines democratic efficacy. This distinction is crucial because it challenges us to think beyond technological capability toward democratic purpose.

Efficiency concerns operational smoothness: faster processing, reduced costs, streamlined workflows, elimination of friction and delays. These metrics are seemingly understandable in commercial contexts where the goal tends to be satisfied customers and profitable operations.

Efficacy concerns purposeful effectiveness: whether processes achieve their intended democratic outcomes, strengthen civic capacity, build trust, enable meaningful participation, and create conditions for legitimate collective decision-making. Democratic efficacy often requires apparent inefficiencies: time for reflection, space for disagreement, opportunities for changing minds.

The efficiency imperative assumes these two concepts align, and that making processes more efficient automatically makes them more effective. However, democratic processes often work precisely because they resist optimization. The "inefficiencies" of extended deliberation, redundant oversight, and built-in friction serve democratic purposes that seamless systems cannot provide.

II. A Framework for Democratic Assessment

Our research and experimentation with the [Digital Democracy Demonstrator](#) and [Digital Democracy Lab](#) drew on Graham Smith's framework for evaluating democratic innovations through both democratic goods and institutional goods. This framework provides a structured way to assess whether AI integration serves broader democratic purposes or merely institutional convenience.

Democratic Goods include:

- **Inclusiveness:** This category includes both presence (diverse participants from different backgrounds) and voice (meaningful opportunities for all participants to speak, be heard, and influence outcomes). AI can theoretically enhance inclusiveness through translation tools or accessibility features, but it can also systematize exclusion through biased training data or design assumptions that favour particular communication styles or disempower others.
- **Popular Control:** This can be defined as genuine citizen influence over agenda-setting and decision-making processes. This is where many AI systems prove most problematic. By virtue of their very

design, they tend to shift decision-making power away from participants toward algorithmic processes and parameters that citizens cannot meaningfully influence or understand.

- **Considered Judgment:** This is comprised of thoughtful, informed, reflective deliberation where decisions emerge from reasoned exchange and mutual learning rather than raw preferences or aggregated opinions. AI can potentially support this by providing access to information, but it can also undermine it by making complex issues appear simpler than they are or by providing authoritative-sounding answers that discourage further questioning.
- **Transparency:** Clarity is needed about how decisions are made and communicated, both for participants (who must understand the purpose, structure, and consequences of their involvement) and the wider public (who need accessible information about the process). AI systems, particularly large language models, pose fundamental challenges to transparency through their black-box nature and proprietary constraints.

Institutional Goods include:

- **Efficiency:** This good can reduce the demands a process places on systems and people. This is where AI most obviously provides benefits. It can enable a reduction of resource requirements, speed up processing, and handle larger volumes of input. The question is whether these efficiency gains come at the expense of democratic goods.
- **Transferability:** How easily an approach can adapt across different political, cultural, or institutional contexts. AI systems often appear highly transferable because they're based on general-purpose technologies, but this apparent universality may mask cultural biases and context-specific design assumptions. Tools are inseparable from the contexts they are used and experienced in; Relative effectiveness in one context cannot certainly predict effectiveness anywhere else.

The crucial insight from applying this framework is that AI integration typically excels at institutional goods while posing risks to democratic goods if integrated uncritically or without substantial (re)design.

III. AI's Genuine Potential Benefits: Carefully Qualified

When thoughtfully designed and implemented with democratic rather than efficiency goals, AI can enhance certain aspects of democratic exchange:

Information Processing and Synthesis: AI can help participants engage with complex topics by processing large volumes of information, identifying patterns, and making expert knowledge more accessible. This works best when participants can examine AI sources and reasoning, understand limitations, and maintain agency over how to interpret and use AI-generated information. The key is treating AI as a tool providing one perspective among many, not as an authoritative synthesizer of truth.

Accessibility and Inclusion: AI tools can potentially reduce barriers to participation through real-time translation, alternative communication formats, or assistance for those with different

communicative abilities. However, these tools must expand rather than standardize participation methods, ensuring they don't impose particular ways of engaging while appearing to be neutral accommodations.

Augmented Expertise: In contexts where human expertise is genuinely limited – particularly smaller communities without access to specialized knowledge – AI might provide broader information access. This requires transparency about AI limitations, clear boundaries around what any particular AI system can and cannot do, and maintaining human agency over how expert information gets interpreted and applied.

Input Processing at Scale: AI tools might help incorporate broader citizen input into smaller deliberative processes, potentially enabling wider participation while maintaining deliberative depth. This requires careful attention to what gets lost in synthesis, how diverse perspectives are preserved, and who makes decisions about categorization and summarization.

IV. AI's Significant Risks: More Extensive Than Often Acknowledged

The risks of AI integration in democratic settings are both more subtle and more extensive than typically recognized:

Bias Amplification and Systematization: AI systems inevitably embed the biases present in their training data, development processes, and deployment contexts. Unlike human facilitators whose biases can be identified and addressed through relationship and dialogue, algorithmic biases become systematized and harder to detect. When presented as neutral or objective, these systems can reinforce exclusion while maintaining an appearance of fairness.

Erosion of Human Agency: Without careful design, AI integration shifts decision-making power from participants toward technical systems. This happens not through dramatic replacement of human judgment but through subtle ways AI shapes options, frames questions, and influences the range of considered possibilities. Participants may retain formal decision-making power while losing substantive control over the decision-making environment.

Atrophy of Critical Thinking: AI outputs often sound authoritative and comprehensive, discouraging the questioning, challenging, and reframing that effective deliberation requires. Rather than augmenting human reasoning, AI tools can create cognitive dependency where people apathetically defer to algorithmic analysis rather than developing their own capacity for critical engagement with complex issues.

Illusion of Transparency: AI systems can appear transparent – showing data sources, providing explanations, offering choices – while actually obscuring the most crucial decisions about system design, training data selection, and algorithmic optimization goals. Participants may feel informed about how an AI tool works while remaining uninformed about why it works, and how it may be shaping their democratic interactions.

Elimination of Meaningful Friction: Democracy benefits from certain inefficiencies that AI optimization systematically eliminates: time to reconsider positions, opportunities for spontaneous insights, space for uncomfortable disagreements, moments of productive confusion that force deeper thinking. Seamless AI-driven experiences can optimize away the very dynamics that enable democratic learning and growth.

V. What This Means for Democratic Practitioners

The implications of this analysis offer an opportunity for democratic practitioners to enhance their criticality and democratically constructive decision-making, design, and facilitation. Here, several key insights can be of particular value for practitioners to bear in mind:

Maintain Healthy Scepticism: The burden of proof should be on AI proponents to demonstrate not just that AI tools can make processes more efficient, but that it genuinely enhances democratic goods without unacceptable trade-offs. Most current proposals fail this test.

Critically Consider Innovation Pressure: The assumption that failure to adopt new technologies indicates stagnation or irrelevance is often wrong in democratic contexts. Democratic institutions may be most innovative when they resist or adapt rather than embrace technological optimization.

Focus on Democratic Rather Than Technological Sophistication: The goal isn't to become expert in AI capabilities but to become expert in recognizing how different tools and approaches serve democratic purposes. Technical sophistication is less important than democratic clarity.

Preserve Agency Over Technological Integration: You have both the right and the responsibility to say no to AI proposals that don't clearly serve democratic purposes, regardless of their technical impressiveness, investment to date, or institutional pressure.

The path forward isn't about rejecting AI entirely or embracing it uncritically. **It's about developing the capacity to distinguish between technological solutions that genuinely serve democratic purposes and those that simply apply efficiency logic to democratic contexts.** This distinction is crucial because it determines whether AI becomes a tool for democratic enhancement or democratic displacement—and the difference may be far more subtle than current discourse suggests.

3 Get Set:

Get familiar (and ready to adapt)
approaches to designing & integrating AI

Some (hopefully useful) "*recipes*" for how to enact effective democracy amidst an efficiency imperative.

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Democracy-in-the-Loop: The Essential Foundation

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Before diving into the specific recipes for navigating, designing, and facilitating AI-embedded democratic exchange, it's crucial to understand the conceptual framework that makes these approaches democratically meaningful rather than merely technically functional. That framework is Democracy-in-the-Loop (DITL). It is the essential "ingredient" that transforms AI from a tool that can undermine democratic exchange into one that might actually enhance it.

What Democracy-in-the-Loop Is (and Isn't)

Democracy-in-the-Loop builds upon – but fundamentally extends – two existing approaches to AI oversight: [Human-in-the-Loop \(HITL\)](#) and [Society-in-the-Loop \(SITL\)](#).

[Human-in-the-Loop](#) approaches involve embedding individual human judgment into AI systems, i.e., having experts oversee or intervene in algorithmic decisions. While valuable, HITL has significant limitations: it rarely specifies which humans are involved, how their oversight is structured, or how their power is accountable. It assumes that individual human judgment is sufficient to ensure AI serves human interests, without addressing questions of whose judgment, representing which perspectives, and accountable to whom.

Society-in-the-Loop attempts to broaden oversight by aligning AI with societal values determined during system development. SITL recognizes that AI should reflect broader social values rather than just expert judgment. However, it typically treats these values as relatively stable inputs determined once during design, rather than as contestable, evolving commitments that require ongoing negotiation. SITL also rarely addresses how "societal values" are determined, whose values count as society's, and how conflicts between different value systems are resolved.

HITL

SITL

Democracy-in-the-Loop goes further by embedding ongoing democratic stewardship directly into both the design and the use of AI systems in democratic contexts. Rather than treating oversight as something that happens during development (SITL) or as sporadic expert intervention (HITL), DITL creates continuous opportunities for participants to question, critique, adjust, and collectively shape how AI systems behave throughout their operation.

This means:

- **Ongoing Contestation:** Participants are provided opportunities to challenge AI outputs, assumptions, and processes in real-time rather than accepting algorithmic authority
- **Collective Agency:** Groups make decisions together about how AI should function rather than individuals using AI as personalized tools
- **Transparent Limitations:** AI constraints, biases, and design compromises are visible and discussable rather than hidden behind seamless interfaces
- **Iterative Adjustment:** Systems evolve based on participant feedback and collective assessment rather than remaining static after deployment

Why DITL Is the Essential Ingredient

Each recipe in this section – whether you’re navigating an AI proposal, designing an AI system, structuring a process, or facilitating a session – requires DITL thinking because without it, you risk creating systems that optimize democratic exchange out of existence.

DITL Preserves Democratic Agency: Commercial AI systems are designed to make decisions for users, optimizing toward predetermined goals. Democratic exchange requires participants to make decisions together, negotiating goals collectively. Without DITL mechanisms, AI integration shifts decision-making power from participants to algorithms, no matter how sophisticated the technology or well-intentioned its creators.

DITL Makes Power (More) Visible: AI systems embed power in their data selection, algorithmic design, and optimization functions. Without DITL, these power structures remain invisible, i.e., participants experience

AI shaping their conversations without understanding how or why. DITL creates opportunities to examine and contest these embedded power dynamics.

DITL Enables Meaningful Friction: Democratic exchange benefits from certain inefficiencies, i.e., time to reconsider positions, moments of productive disagreement, opportunities for collective sense-making. AI optimization systematically eliminates these frictions. DITL approaches deliberately introduce meaningful friction points that create space for democratic deliberation rather than streamlined decision-making.

DITL Supports Ongoing Learning: Democracy isn't just about making good decisions. It is also about building civic capacities. DITL transforms AI integration from a technical convenience into an opportunity for collective learning about technology, power, and democratic decision-making.

Some Core Mechanisms of DITL

While we anticipate there are other mechanisms that will be uncovered and added with further experimentation, our initial model of DITL operates through several interconnected mechanisms that you'll see threaded throughout the recipes:

1. Meaningful Frictions

These are intentionally designed disruptions that slow down interaction and prompt reflection rather than enabling seamless efficiency. Meaningful frictions might include:

- Requiring collective rather than individual AI prompting
- Making data source selection visible and contestable
- Showing AI decision-making processes rather than just outputs
- Creating pauses for assessment before accepting AI recommendations

The key is that these frictions serve democratic purposes. They create space for deliberation, enable questioning, and preserve participant agency rather than simply being technical annoyances.

2. Contestable Functions

AI systems designed with DITL in mind allow participants to challenge how the system works, not just what it produces. This means:

- Visible design choices that can be questioned
- Adjustable parameters that participants can collectively modify
- Alternative approaches that can be explored
- Exit options when AI fails to serve democratic purposes

3. Collective Intervention Points

Rather than personalized AI experiences, DITL creates moments where groups must collectively decide how AI should behave:

- Which information sources to prioritize
- How to frame questions or prompts
- Whether to accept or reject AI outputs
- How to interpret and apply AI-generated information

4. Transparent Limitations

DITL makes AI constraints explicit rather than hiding them:

- What the system can and cannot do
- What biases are embedded in training data
- What design compromises were made and why
- What remains uncertain or contested

How DITL Shows Up in the Recipes

The recipes that follow represent our current understanding of how best to apply DITL based on designing, deploying, and analyzing the Digital Democracy Lab across multiple contexts. They're starting points rather than endpoints. They are flexible and modular frameworks you can adapt, question, and improve based on your own experience. That said, they share a common conceptual foundation that AI in democratic settings must be designed and deployed to support rather than replace the messy, sometimes inefficient, vital work of democratic exchange.

Navigate a Demand, Request, or Opportunity To Use AI

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OUTCOME: A clear and intentional decision about whether to proceed with AI integration and, if so, how.

When someone suggests incorporating AI into your democratic process—whether it's a commissioner excited about innovation, a colleague who's heard about efficiency gains, or your own curiosity about new possibilities—this recipe helps you navigate that moment thoughtfully. The goal isn't to become an AI expert, but to remain a democracy expert who can critically and constructively evaluate technological proposals.

WHAT YOU'LL NEED

To understand the request, demand, or opportunity:

- One clear description of what's being proposed, in writing if possible
- Insight into the motivations driving the request, both stated and implied
- Clarity regarding your current democratic process and expectations, held up for honest examination
- Time for thinking; More than may initially feel necessary
- Your core democratic principles, framed with precision

For stakeholder conversations:

- Partners willing to listen and think aloud with you about power, participation, and purpose
- Honest assessment of your organization's capacity for experimentation
- Space to discuss what could go wrong without shutting down the possibility of proceeding

To critically evaluate the request, demand, or opportunity:

- Questions that push the analysis beyond claims of efficiencies and toward an exploration of the democratic substance of the opportunity
- Honest view, informed by a degree of critical digital literacy, of (1) what AI system or tool is designed to do, by and for whom, using what inputs and design approaches; and (2) what it actually does and doesn't do for those within and beyond the target consumer groups.
- Alternative approaches that might serve similar democratic intentions
- Willingness to sit with uncertainty about outcomes and candour to communicate questions, hesitations, and concerns.

PREPARATION

Step 1: Understand What's Actually Being Asked/Offered

Before reacting to any AI opportunity, spend time understanding what's really being asked and why. AI requests rarely come in neutral packages. They're often wrapped in assumptions about innovation, efficiency, or competitive pressure.

Consider what problem is AI supposed to solve in this situation. Is this about improving democratic outcomes, reducing costs, appearing cutting-edge, addressing genuine participant needs, or something else entirely? Oftentimes, AI implementations are proposed simply as *solutions* in search of a problem and as a result, it is actually not often the fit-for-purpose tool you might really need for the problem(s) you actually have. Write down or discuss with someone the explicit goals you're really aiming to achieve as a democratic practitioner and the implicit pressures you're sensing.

Pay attention to the language being used and any (mis)alignments you recognise between the claims being made and the problem(s) you're trying to navigate. Consider the following questions and how the answers that emerge might lend themselves to assessing the fitness of any proposal to integrate AI.

- What is the problem being addressed? What factors produce it and how does it manifest?
- In which ways is this technology fit-for-purpose to help address the problem at hand?
- Who gains from the implementation of this technology and how (citizens, government, companies, third sector; *in improved services, access to data, monetary gains, prestige, etc.*)?
- How would you know the technology implementation had been a success?
- What basic things do you need to know about how any pre-existing elements of the system may have been built, where do they come from, how were they accessed, and the ethics that informed their creation?

Step 2: Assess Your Own Democratic Principles and Expectations

Before considering what AI might add, develop a precise understanding of what your existing process is meant to accomplish democratically. Not just in terms of outputs, like reports, recommendations, or decisions, but the democratic goods that are meant to emerge throughout the process itself. For example, is your deliberative process engaging in a neighbourhood experiencing a lot of polarization? Then you might lay the focus on creating a better and more thoughtful debate between citizens (as in 'considered judgement'). Is your context one where citizens have lost faith and trust in public institutions and the political system? Then the focus might lie in creating situations where citizens feel more empowered over their own day to day lives (as in 'popular control'). Your own specific context will be pivotal for understanding how to design it, where to put the focus and how technology could integrate in that. Graham Smith describes *inclusivity, popular control, considered judgement, or transparency* as key democratic goods determining the quality of deliberative settings ([Graham Smith, 2009](#)). Maybe there are other democratic goods you feel are essential to the kind of process you aim to carry out?

Consider what creates trust among participants. Often it's transparency, predictability, the sense that contributions matter. Consider what enables genuine deliberation. Usually it's time, skilled facilitation, opportunities to reconsider initial positions. Consider what makes the process feel legitimate. Typically, it's good-faith sharing of power, unpredetermined outcomes, and meaningful inclusion of diverse voices.

These goods emerge from careful attention to relationships, to process, and to the conditions that allow collective decision-making to develop. AI integration that strengthens these goods deserves serious consideration. AI integration that hinders or outright eliminates them requires scepticism, regardless of other benefits the AI might offer.

Step 3: Interrogate the Efficiency Assumption

Most AI integration proposals arrive carrying the assumption that efficiency represents inherent value. But democratic processes often require what appears inefficient from the outside: redundancy that builds understanding, tangents that reveal unexpected connections, conflict that forces deeper examination of assumptions.

The question isn't whether AI can make your process more efficient; it almost certainly can. The question is whether that efficiency serves or undermines the democratic work you're trying to accomplish. Speed isn't always a democratic good. Neither is frictionless consensus or streamlined decision-making.

Consider where your process may benefit from apparent inefficiencies. The extended discussion that seems to circle back but actually allows participants to develop more sophisticated positions. The moments of confusion that creates space for previously unconsidered perspectives or insights to emerge. The technical complexity or experiential awkwardness that forces collective slowing down and deeper thinking about goals.

Step 4: Evaluate Capacity and Context

AI integration always involves experimentation, even with well-tested systems. This requires organizational and cultural capacity for uncertainty; relationships strong enough to navigate different technical expectations and failures, time flexibility for learning and adjustment, stakeholders who understand that democratic innovation sometimes means accepting imperfection as an essential characteristic of learning and democracy itself.

It also entails a significant investment in time and resources to introduce any new digital system. This raises important questions about long-term capacity: does your organisation have the infrastructure and support to maintain and adapt the technology over time? Introducing a new tool also creates its own momentum. Once a digital system has been purchased or developed, there is often a tendency to justify the investment - leading organisations to feel locked-in and to use the system more broadly than initially intended, regardless of its actual fit. This kind of path dependency can limit flexibility and obscure critical reflection on whether the tool continues to serve its democratic purpose.

Consider your participants as well. Will AI integration feel empowering or alienating? Will it enhance their sense of agency or undermine it? Will it catalyse critical thinking, apathy, or distrust? The answers depend not just on technology but on the legitimacy and trustworthiness of the technology you're working with along and the designers, developers, and companies that built it, your participants and peers' relationship to digital tools, their trust in your judgment, as well as their tolerance for potentially non-linear and iterative processes and tech that are constructively inefficient, glitchy, and flawed.

Step 5: Assess the Effects on the Democratic Character of the Process

For any AI integration proposal, work through this fundamental question: *What would this do to the democratic character of our process?*

What capacities would AI add? Perhaps it can enhance the process by synthesizing large volumes of input, identifying patterns across complex information, or supporting multilingual participation. These aren't inherently democratic goods, but they might serve democratic purposes under the right conditions.

What human capacities would AI replace? Maybe time for individual reflection, face-to-face discussions, disagreements, and reframings, or the ability to change process direction based on emerging insights. If these characteristics are vital to your principles and expectations of Democracy, then the addition of AI in such a case might be overtly problematic.

What would be lost entirely? Opportunities for spontaneous discovery, the texture of generative and genuine interaction and discourse between participants who are all navigating a degree of uncertainty, accountability that is held in relationships rather than algorithms. These losses might represent acceptable or unacceptable trade-offs. The point here is to be clear about whether AI will actually help or hinder the democratic character of your democratic exchange process; whether AI integration will serve the democratic goods you're committed to fostering.

If the trade-offs don't clearly favour democratic quality, if you can't articulate how AI enhances rather than undermines democratic goods, or if the proposal feels driven more by technological possibility than democratic need, these are strong signals to pause or decline.

Step 6: Explore Alternative Approaches

Before committing to technological solutions, explore whether other democratic innovations or alternative facilitative approaches might address underlying challenges more directly. Fit-for-purpose facilitation techniques, additional human resources, and careful process (re)design all offer more effective ways to address certain problems without compromising the democratic character of the process than just relying on technologically to resolve everything.

Sometimes the most thoughtful response to an AI opportunity is solving the core challenge through democratic rather than technological means. This isn't technological aversion; it's democratic prioritization.

Step 7: Make Your Decision

Your evaluation should lead to a decision you can articulate clearly and defend publicly:

Proceed with specific parameters: Yes, if we can ensure particular democratic safeguards and oversight.

Proceed experimentally: Yes, as a carefully bounded pilot that allows us to understand democratic impacts before broader implementation.

Decline with alternatives: No to AI tool use, but here are other ways we might address your underlying concerns.

Decline entirely: No, because this doesn't align with our democratic commitments or our current context.

SIGNS OF A GOOD DECISION

- You can explain how your decision will advance democratic goods rather than only institutional goods.
- Stakeholders understand not just what you've decided but why.
- If moving forward, you have realistic expectations and clear success criteria. If declining, you've offered constructive alternatives addressing legitimate concerns.
- Most importantly, you feel confident that your decision prioritises the democratic goods you intend to protect and advance. Your final decision should reflect your role as a steward of democratic quality. This sometimes means saying no to appealing innovations that would compromise the very thing you're trying to serve.

If you've found ways that AI can advance your intended democratic goods, then you might find it helpful to consider how to:

- [Design an effective AI for democratic exchange](#)
- [Design an effective AI-embedded democratic exchange process](#)
- [Facilitate an effective AI-embedded democratic exchange process](#)

Design an Effective AI for Democratic Exchange

OUTCOME: An AI system designed to enhance and constructively augment rather than substitute or harm democratic exchange

Designing AI tools and systems that support democratic exchange requires thinking backwards from democratic goods rather than forwards from technological possibilities. The challenge lies in creating AI systems that invite scrutiny rather than demanding trust, that can constructively slow discourse and decision-making down rather than inherently speeding it up, and that make human agency tangible rather than obscuring it. Importantly, it may also require accepting that your first attempt will be rough, limited, and error-prone; However, these imperfections—recognised and engaged with intentionally—can become valuable democratic features rather than technical failures.

NOTE: As with the other recipes and insights presented in this handbook, it is important to note that they are derived from the lessons learned through our work on the [Digital Democracy Lab](#) (DDL), an experimental deliberative process, and the [Digital Democracy Demonstrator](#) (DDD), an AI platform intended to experiment with augmentation and enhancement of democratic exchange. With this in mind, we will use the Demonstrator (DDD) and Lab (DDL) as reference points in the following recipe in order to help illustrate and clarify what we mean. We do not suggest that you need to replicate or adopt these exact tools. Rather, understanding how these systems were designed and used in practice can help inform your own design and development processes.

The DDL and DDD were developed within the KT4D project by an interdisciplinary team of democratic practitioners, designers, technologists and researchers. This collaboration enabled us to test AI integration in a live, facilitated deliberative setting, with real participants—including citizens, policymakers, civil society actors and technical experts.

WHAT YOU'LL NEED

For a solid foundation from which to begin:

- Collaborative and communicative technical partners
 - *Ideal*: Technical partners who understand why and how a democratic AI system is—and should be—different from a commercial AI system.
 - *Minimum*: Technical partners who are patient, willing to listen, and able to cede relevant design and development decisions to your own expertise on the democratic exchange you intend to enable.
 - *Unacceptable*: Technical partners who are insistent on selling you particular solution(s) you recognise as ill-fitting to your context or specificity of your problem; unwilling or unable to explain particular functionalities; and/or unwilling or unable to (re)design the technology in order to emphasize, integrate, or remove elements you see as necessary to enable the effectiveness of the democratic exchange.
- Clear understanding of—and commitment to—the democratic goods and institutional goods your process aims to achieve
- Time for iterative testing with real democratic participants

To navigate the lack of transparency (blackbox) of commercial (and even open source) AI systems:

- Strategy for working within corporate AI tools while maintaining democratic values. This may include onboarding a trusted source of expertise to help you understand ethical, environmental, and fitness of a system under consideration
- Plan for making visible and understandable that which can be made visible and understandable as well as creating work-arounds to render what seemingly can't be made visible and understandable available and problematized in some kind of way; even if just naming it as a problem participants ought to consider
- Approach to honest communication about system limitations and your own design compromises
- Framework for ensuring participant agency despite underlying technical opacity

To enable effective collaboration with technical teams:

- Language to frame democratic requirements in terms technical partners can understand
- Questions that help surface hidden assumptions in technical proposals, best-practices, and norms.
- Methods for testing democratic impact alongside technical functionality
- Structure for ongoing dialogue between democratic and technical expertise
- Patience for explaining why "perfect" user experience might undermine democratic goals. Here, it may be useful to find a trusted intermediary with overlapping experience in design and democratic practice to assist these translation processes

For the system architecture:

- Backend frameworks and user interface design which makes AI decision-making visible and contestable
- Approach to data curation that participants can examine and critique
- Method for incorporating participant values into AI outputs
- Design for meaningful friction points that invite engagement
- Plan for handling the inevitable technical failures openly and constructively

For ongoing refinement:

- Process for capturing participant feedback about AI interaction
- Mechanism for distinguishing productive friction from unproductive glitches
- Documentation of design decisions that can be questioned and revised
- Partnership structure that allows rapid iteration during development

PREPARATION

Step 1: Start With Democratic Purpose, Not Technical Capability

Your role is ensuring that technological power serves democratic purposes rather than substituting technological optimisation for democratic decision-making. In crafting the Digital Democracy Demonstrator, the first design principle was, therefore, that it [add value to democratic exchange](#).

To do this effectively requires understanding what democratic value actually looks like in practice. Before considering any technical specifications, you must establish clear answers to questions of: *What democratic goods your process aims to foster? What kinds of interactions do you want to enable? What should participants be able to do together that they couldn't do before?*

With the KT4D Demonstrator, the primary intention was to use AI to support engagement with topics that might otherwise appear too complex or overly technical for participants to meaningfully deliberate on. The proposed value here—democratically—was to afford complex policy discussions pared down to values-based conversations amongst participants that could be informed and translated by an appropriately trained AI system.

However, the actual value, which we learned through testing, was in the AI system's blunders, oversimplifications, and transparent limitations as an “expert”. While the AI's sleek visual and linguistic aesthetics suggested a level of expertise worth deferring to, its limitations afforded immediate scepticism amongst the participants and inspired them to think critically and collectively about both the topic of the deliberation as well as the role and impact of the AI on the quality of the democratic discourse.

In effect, the ethical, intellectual, and intelligence failures of the AI, which are usually compensated for and made less apparent by seamless user interfaces, were made transparent. Participants could recognise the

flaws with relative ease compared to typical commercial AIs, and were encouraged by such observations to think critically about the conversations the AI was framing and reframing for them.

The *flaws* of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator enabled participants to think deeply about how deliberations and participatory processes, more generally, are shaped by the data, designers, questions, and assumptions that are relied upon to frame and effectuate them.

Defining and refining the democratic purpose shapes every subsequent technical decision. If your goal is to enable more informed deliberation, your AI may need to surface nuance, indeterminacy, and disagreement, rather than resolve it. If your goal is inclusive participation, your AI may need to accommodate different ways of engaging rather than standardizing, embedding, and imposing them. And, importantly, how you achieve these democratic intentions may rely on the technology, but not on the attributes of the technology that you might assume would be most advantageous, advanced, or helpful.

Step 2: Proceed with Collaborative and Constructive Scepticism

A. Collaborate With Technical Partners Who Care about Democratic Values and Constraints

Building democratically effective AI requires technical partners who listen, can recognise that democratic technologies may have different success criteria than commercial ones, are open to an unconventional process of developing democratically effective technologies, and who can work creatively within design, resource, and timeline constraints.

As part of the KT4D project, our collaboration with Hybrid Core, a Belgian technology consultancy that develops hybrid intelligence systems combining human and artificial cognition, involved months of iterative co-design where democratic and technical expertise informed each other. Technical constraints shaped what democratic interventions were possible. Resource limitations forced creative solutions. Democratic requirements pushed technical innovation in unexpected directions, often away from "best practices" as understood in commercial development.

When they proposed technical solutions, we asked how those affected democratic dynamics. When we requested democratic features, the technical team explained the technical implications and cost constraints. The breakthrough in our collaboration came when we reframed frictions, inefficiencies, and glitches not as compromises but as innovation opportunities we should pursue purposefully.

This kind of partnership requires clear communication about non-technical values from the start, as well as honest discussion about resource needs. Technical partners need to understand why transparency might be more important than user experience, why inefficiency and frictions might serve democratic purposes, why participants need to be able to critique and potentially deconstruct the system, and why budget limitations might require deliberate decisions about the democratic scope and utility of the technologies being developed.

It is important to establish regular check-ins focused specifically on democratic impact rather than just technical functionality. Ask questions like: "*How are participants experiencing agency in this interaction?*" "*What assumptions about user behaviour are we building in?*" "*Where might participants want more control over the*

process?" "How do we make our limitations transparent and contestable?" "What would break if participants used this differently than intended?" "How do we explain our limitations without undermining the democratic purpose?" These conversations help technical partners understand that democratic AI is a genuinely different category of technology implementation.

B. Learn to Question Technical Proposals Constructively

Working effectively with technical teams requires developing language to question proposals in ways that generate dialogue rather than defensiveness. Technical partners often have deep expertise but may not understand how their decisions affect democratic dynamics, especially when those decisions are driven by resource constraints or system limitations.

For example, when our technical partners proposed using profiles to enable Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), we pushed back not on the technical approach but on its democratic implications with questions like: "How do we ensure participants can understand how this works and what data and design-decisions it depends on? How do participants understand and critique their own profiling? What happens when the AI categories don't match how participants see themselves? How do we prevent this from reinforcing echo chambers? How do we make the limitations of our approach visible, discussable, and contestable?"

These questions helped reveal innovative opportunities for democratic enhancement. The profiling quiz in the Demonstrator emerged not as a seamless user experience but as an explicit friction point where participants could examine and critique algorithmic categorization. The decision to show all data sources came from asking, "How do participants evaluate the credibility and bias of information sources?" along with a limitation on the number of sources we could find and include legally.

To facilitate this, you will need to learn to frame your democratic requirements clearly: Participants need opportunities to understand and influence how the system works, even when we're working with limited transparency; Complexity needs to serve democratic purposes, even if it makes participants' experiences more awkward or challenging.

Step 3: Design for Transparency and Accountability

The second principle guiding the design of our Demonstrator was to enable transparency and accountability.

One of the fundamental tensions in designing democratic AI lies in working with existing AI technologies, like ChatGPT, which are explicitly secretive and protective about their data sourcing and training. Effective democratic exchange, on the other hand, requires participants to trust the soundness and fairness of the process and the information that underpins it. As such, using these commercial technologies in any way within democratic exchange necessitates a baseline scepticism and consistent critical reflection regarding the presumed acceptable mechanisms, constraints, and features of the technology, which may be commercially acceptable, but could be anti-democratic in/by design.

In our experience developing the Demonstrator, we could not fully understand and expose the data, training, and parameters which shape how an AI like ChatGPT reaches its conclusions, but we could be honest, transparent, and explicit about those limitations. So, we developed a view of what we called the AI's

"metabolism": representations of the core operational components of the AI that participants could examine and critique.

This included four main elements: (1) how participants were profiled based on a 30-question quiz about technology, society and economics; (2) how data was retrieved through RAG from our limited curated sources; (3) how GPT-4 generated responses based on these inputs; and (4) which specific sources informed those responses.

Making each component visible required specific design choices that differed markedly from commercial AI experiences, and that often highlighted our limitations rather than hiding them. Participant profiling became an explicit, discussable, and contestible activity rather than hidden tracking. Data sources were curated rather than vast and invisible; we used exactly 10 sources each of newspaper articles, peer-reviewed papers, and policy documents that participants could browse and critique, partly because that's all we could afford to properly license and, therefore, ethically use. We were also explicit about who picked the data sources and the framework we created to select them: participants could thereby recognize and critique how and by whom the AI's internal logics were biased.

In the Demonstrator interface, participants could click through different sections to explore these metabolic components. Videos explained how profiles were created (by us, using academic frameworks, not by AI), how RAG worked to connect profiles with relevant data sources, and how GPT-4 synthesized responses. Most of the videos were produced using AI-generated text-to-speech and visuals, which ended up feeling corporate and promotional rather than critical. This incongruence with the rest of the critical experience became a valuable friction point, which spurred participants to feel uncertain about the claims of certainty described in the videos about RAG and the Demonstrator.

This transparency came with real trade-offs and revealed real constraints. Transparent and frictional systems can feel more awkward than seamlessly opaque ones. Participants needed time to understand what they were looking at. Some found the profiling quiz limiting, the video explanations simplistic, or our data source selection too narrow. But these apparent inefficiencies and limitations served a democratic purpose; they allowed participants to develop informed opinions about how the AI worked, what we'd been forced to compromise on, and whether they trusted our imperfect processes.

These workarounds should not be seen as permission or acceptance that Large Language Models like GPT-4 should continue with their opaque practices; However, until genuine transparency is possible, finding space for honesty about limitations and constraints is essential. Participants need to understand what has already been determined for them and by whom, what they can and cannot influence, and what is visible and what remains hidden.

As democratic practitioners working with technical teams, consider how you might frame these constraints honestly and explicitly: Where can we create visibility and participant control? Where must we acknowledge – but not necessarily accept – limitations? How do we turn our constraints into democratic features?

Step 4: Embed Democratic Stewardship Throughout

A. Learn and Apply a Democracy-in-the-Loop Approach

The third design principle for the Digital Democracy Demonstrator was that it operationalises **democratic stewardship** of the process by establishing a Democracy-in-the-Loop approach to AI.

Democracy-in-the-Loop (DITL) is a concept of embedding democratic intervention points into technology to ensure that as an AI relies on certain logics and parameters to make decisions, those logics and decisions are shaped by democratically determined values, principles, norms, and expectations. Operationalising DITL ensures that AI systems remain responsive to democratic input and shaped by democratic values rather than the predetermined optimization functions, which are typical of commercial engineers and designers. This requires building intervention points where participants can question, adjust, and collectively shape how the AI behaves, while being honest about the system's constraints and your own design limitations.

In the Demonstrator, this meant requiring collective rather than individual interaction with an AI chatbot. Participants had to collaboratively craft a single question-prompt rather than querying the system individually. They could choose which data sources to prioritise: newspaper articles, policy papers, academic sources, or a combination. They could challenge AI outputs and request alternative approaches based on different source selections.

The collective prompt-engineering process became one of our most valuable friction points, partly by necessity. Unlike typical chatbot interactions where individuals receive personalized responses, the entire group of participants had to use one chatbot to negotiate what question to ask, how to frame it, and which sources to draw from. This created natural space for discussion about values, assumptions, and what kind of information would actually be useful for their deliberation.

A key learning from deployment was that the profile system needed to be redesigned to encourage finding common ground rather than reinforcing divisions. Participants valued understanding how their perspectives related to others rather than being placed in fixed categories. The rigid categorization was partly a limitation of our approach; we'd created profiles using rule-based algorithms rather than more sophisticated methods, which could have afforded more collective exchange rather than individual judgement.

These design choices deliberately introduced friction into AI interaction, sometimes by design and sometimes by necessity. Instead of fast, personalized responses, participants experienced slower, collectively negotiated ones. Instead of seamless user experience, they encountered opportunities to pause, discuss, and redirect the process based on what they were learning together.

B. Design Meaningful Frictions, Allow for Generative Glitches, and Announce Errors

One of our key learnings from deployment was that imperfections in the tool can actually create meaningful, trust-inducing frictions that encourage critical thinking. Too much polish can reduce critical engagement with the technology. When participants encountered limitations, unfinished features, or clearly improvised

solutions in the Demonstrator, these moments often became the most valuable parts of the democratic process.

AI systems used in democratic exchange seem to benefit from some types of inconvenience, glitches, and friction because perfect, seamless performance seems to undermine their democratic purpose. Glossy, unflawed experiences and aesthetics may align with commercial norms of convenience and consumption, but they tend to afford indifference and apathy rather than critique – or even trust – toward the automatically generated materials.

As a beta version being deployed for the first time, the Demonstrator produced both intentional, meaningful frictions and unexpected glitches. Some of these flaws were not intentionally designed but proved to be generative tensions, offering insights into the system's underlying logic and limitations. These unintended disruptions became moments of revelation, allowing participants to better grasp how systems function.

However, we learned to distinguish between meaningful friction and unproductive glitches. Some technical failures disrupted workflow without adding depth to discussion, becoming irritations rather than catalysts for engagement. Keep in mind that a malfunctioning system doesn't automatically generate critical thinking or meaningful deliberation; it can just be badly designed.

Our experience showed that transparency about limitations and resource constraints builds trust more than false claims of comprehensiveness or perfection. When the Demonstrator operated in a way or produced outputs that felt inadequate or biased based on design and technological limitations that the participants understood, they engaged in deeper, more critical conversations about the democratic values at stake and AI's proper role.

For example, in Dublin, software developers testing the Demonstrator pushed back on our AI-generated explainer videos, finding them overly simplified and corporate-sounding. These moments weren't inherently design failures because they opened up conversations about values, assumptions, and the compromises we'd had to make in development, which, to some extent, are the kinds of decisions implicit within any commercial AI one might use.

→ Don't present the AI systems or the outputs they produce as polished solutions, but as starting points for discussion. Create explicit opportunities for participants to collectively evaluate and potentially reject what the AI produces and be honest about where system limitations reflect design errors, resource constraints, or technological/democratic compromises rather than effective design choices.

C. Select, Explain, and make your Data Sources Contestable

Unlike commercial AI systems that train on vast datasets, the kinds of AI used in democratic exchange require careful curation of sources that participants can examine and evaluate. This curation process itself becomes a site of democratic decision-making; it also reveals the practical constraints of working with limited budgets and legal compliance requirements.

For the Demonstrator, we compiled three distinct categories of sources: newspaper articles, peer-reviewed journal articles, and policy papers from the European Commission.

All 30 sources focused on the theme of labour market dynamics in the AI era since labour and AI were the primary policy topics explored in our experimental deliberations. We made these sources completely visible to participants, allowing them to browse document lists, examine titles and sources, and access full-text documents through the interface.

At the time of deployment, the Demonstrator was still in beta version, and the process of acquiring ethically, legally, and licensing-compliant data posed significant challenges. As a result, we launched with only 10 sources per category; far fewer than ideal, but all we could afford to properly license and legally clear. However, this constraint became a transparency feature: participants could see exactly what limitations we were working within rather than assuming comprehensive coverage.

This transparency about data sources and our limitations led to culturally fascinating discussions about trustworthiness and bias. In our Krakow workshop, participants were hesitant to trust governmental sources, preferring independent research or journalism. In Brussels, policymakers brought different assumptions about the credibility of academic versus policy sources. Making our curation process and constraints visible allowed these preferences to become part of the democratic conversation rather than hidden assumptions built into the system.

The challenge lies in balancing comprehensiveness with manageability while being honest about resource constraints. Too few sources limit the AI's capacity to provide useful synthesis. Too many sources become impossible for participants to meaningfully evaluate and potentially too expensive to properly license. We found that 10 sources per category did not provide enough diversity for useful AI outputs, but they did remain reviewable by participants and affordable for our budget. We were always clear this was a compromise rather than an ideal solution and suspect there would be a better balance of number of sources, diversity of sources, and number of sources that remain reviewable that could be achieved.

Step 5: Conscientiously Test with Real Democratic Practitioners and Participants

AI systems like this should not be designed in isolation. In order to serve as tools that can enhance, rather than hinder, democratic exchange they must be tested by other democratic practitioners and with people actually engaging in democratic exchange. This testing reveals gaps between design intentions and realities of democratic deliberation, contestation, and participation. However, involving real participants in experimental AI testing carries significant ethical responsibilities that must be addressed before, during, and after any testing process. Participants must understand they're engaging with experimental, unproven technology that may behave unpredictably. We were extremely careful to explain that the Demonstrator was a beta system with known limitations, that their interactions might not work as expected, and that the primary purpose was learning about AI's effect on democratic exchange rather than solving the policy problem we put forward. Never position or frame experimental AI as more capable or reliable than it actually is.

Our testing across four different contexts—citizens in Madrid and Krakow, policymakers in Brussels, and technologists in Dublin—revealed how the same imperfect system functioned differently depending on participant expectations and comfort levels. Citizens approached the profiling exercise with curiosity about algorithmic categorization and concerns about privacy. Policymakers focused on governance implications and regulatory questions. Technologists examined technical implementation details.

The Brussels workshop revealed that our initial design didn't adequately address power dynamics: participants worried the system might cement existing inequalities rather than challenge them. The citizen workshops in Madrid and Krakow highlighted cultural differences in trust toward different types of sources, as well as practical issues with device access and GDPR compliance.

This feedback shaped ongoing design decisions within our resource constraints. When participants found the profiling categories too limiting, we added discussions about the limitations of algorithmic categorization rather than rebuilding the entire system. When they wanted more control over data source selection, we built in additional intervention points that worked within our existing architecture. When they questioned particular curation choices, we made our decision-making process and constraints more transparent. Plan for substantial revisions based on participant feedback but also be realistic about which changes are possible within your resource constraints.

SIGNS OF AN EFFECTIVE AI-BASED INTERVENTION

- Participants can explain how the AI system works, what its limitations are, and why they do or don't trust its processes.
- Technical partners understand and support the democratic goals informing design decisions, even when those decisions create additional work or complexity.
- The AI system creates opportunities for meaningful human agency rather than eliminating them.
- Use of AI enhances rather than replaces human judgment.
- Participants feel more capable of informed deliberation and disagreement, not less capable of independent thought.
- Frictions become learning opportunities rather than system breakdowns, and limitations become discussion points rather than hidden secrets.
- Most importantly, the AI serves the democratic process rather than deciding it. Participants maintain control over how the technology shapes their collective reasoning, and they understand what they're controlling and what they're not.

Design an Effective AI-Embedded Democratic Exchange

OUTCOME: A democratic process that meaningfully integrates AI while preserving and enhancing the quality of democratic exchange

Designing AI-embedded democratic exchange requires thinking systematically about how technology serves, rather than replaces, the messy, iterative work of democracy. The challenge isn't technical but democratic. Create processes where AI augments human judgment while participants maintain agency over both the technology and their collective decisions. Rather than thinking the work is done when the AI is created, maintain a constant focus on the architecture of democratic exchange processes themselves. Recognise that the most sophisticated AI becomes meaningless without careful attention to the democratic interactions and dynamics it's meant to support.

NOTE: As with the other recipes and insights presented in this handbook, it is important to note that they are derived from the lessons learned through our work on the [Digital Democracy Lab](#) (DDL), an experimental deliberative process, and the [Digital Democracy Demonstrator](#) (DDD), an AI platform intended to experiment with augmentation and enhancement of democratic exchange. With this in mind, we will use the Demonstrator (DDD) and Lab (DDL) as reference points in the following recipe in order to help illustrate and clarify what we mean. We do not suggest that you need to replicate or adopt these exact tools. Rather, understanding how these systems were designed and used in practice can help inform your own design and development processes.

The DDL and DDD were developed within the KT4D project by an interdisciplinary team of democratic practitioners, designers, technologists and researchers. This collaboration enabled us to test AI integration in a live, facilitated deliberative setting, with real participants—including citizens, policymakers, civil society actors and technical experts.

WHAT YOU'LL NEED

To centre democratic purpose:

- Clear articulation of what democratic goods your process aims to foster
- Understanding of when and how your process may benefit from meaningful inefficiencies
- Insight into your participants' relationship to digital tools, AI, and democracy (conceptually and practically)
- Honest assessment of what existing analog processes already achieve well without technology

To design meaningful frictions:

- Strategy for distinguishing meaningful frictions, glitches, and inconveniences from unproductive irritations
- Framework for creating and integrating contestable intervention points when participants can question and redirect the process and the AI
- Plan for making AI decision-making and rationale visible and contestable rather than seamless and unexplained
- Approach to designing collective rather than individualized AI interactions

To design the process:

- Strategies and methods to integrate analogue and digital components in democratically constructive ways
- Framework for collective ongoing critique and validation of both process and outputs
- Design for iterative refinement based on participant input

For ongoing stewardship:

- Facilitation capacity that can navigate both democratic and technological complexity (as described in Facilitating an Effective AI-Embedded Democratic Exchange)
- Monitoring approach that captures democratic impact, not just technical functionality
- Plan for adapting process design based on what emerges in unique contexts and during implementation

PREPARATION

Step 1: Design for Democratic Purpose, Not Technological Possibility

Before considering any AI integration, establish exactly what democratic work your process needs to accomplish. This goes beyond outputs – policy recommendations or decisions – to include and prioritise the democratic effects that emerge through the process itself: trust-building, problem (re)framing, perspective-taking.

Our experience with the Digital Democracy Lab taught us that AI's most valuable contribution wasn't generating better policy proposals but creating opportunities for critical engagement with complex topics and the ways they can be framed with the data and questions that surround them. The AI's confident but limited responses became conversation starters rather than conversation enders, prompting participants to examine both the substance and the technological mediation of their discussions.

As you begin to design your own process, ask yourself: *“What kinds of democratic interaction does my process need to enable?”* *“What should participants be able to do together that they couldn't accomplish individually?”* *“How do you want people to relate to information, to each other, and to the collective engagement process itself?”*

The answers to these questions and, more importantly, clarity regarding the democratic goods your process is meant to afford, should drive every subsequent design choice.

Step 2: Design the Process Before the Technology

The most democratically effective AI integrations emerge from careful process design rather than technological sophistication. The technology should fit within the intentions of the democratic exchange process. You shouldn't be designing your democratic exchange process to accommodate or achieve the intentions of the technology. Design your democratic exchange process first, identifying where AI might be able to enhance specific deliberative, participatory, contestational, or co-creative ambitions.

In the Digital Democracy Lab, we structured the process around three distinct phases: Understanding (building Critical Digital Literacy), Engaging (interacting with the demonstrator), and Validating (collective assessment of both process and outputs). Each phase required different kinds of individual and collective interactions: individual reflection, augmented research, expert input, and collective reasoning. The AI served specific functions within this broader process rather than driving the entire exchange.

Consider designing your process around different modes of engagement and interaction which are important to inform and shape conscientious democratic exchange:

Individual: Moments for personal reflection, values clarification, initial position development. AI might support research or perspective-broadening here but shouldn't replace the individual thinking time democracy requires.

AI Augmented: Opportunities for participants to interrogate information or perspectives beyond their immediate knowledge provided by AI. This works best when AI limitations are visible and participants can critique what they're being offered.

Expert Guidance: Integration of domain knowledge through human experts, AI systems, or curated resources. Again, the key is making expertise visible and contestable rather than authoritative and final.

Collective: Space and time for deliberation, disagreement, negotiation, questioning, reframing, and consensus-building that emerge during group interactions.

Design explicit transitions between these modes. Participants need to understand when they're thinking individually versus when they're engaging with AI-mediated information versus when they're exploring ideas and options collectively.

Step 3: Create Meaningful Friction, Not Seamless Efficiency

One of our most important discoveries from designing the [Digital Democracy Demonstrator](#) and [Digital Democracy Lab](#) was that AI's imperfections often could serve democratic purposes better than polished performance would have. Technical limitations that forced collective rather than individual interaction, data source constraints that made curation decisions visible, and AI responses that seemed oversimplified all became valuable friction points that enhanced rather than undermined democratic engagement.

But friction must be meaningful, *i.e.*, disruptions, inefficiencies, and inconveniences that encourage democratic reflection rather than mere irritation. Meaningful friction serves specific democratic purposes. They offer [opportunities to reflect and more consciously examine the values that are central in making policy determinations](#). Such frictions offer moments where participants must collectively decide how the AI should behave, what sources to prioritize, what assumptions to question. In our process, collective prompt engineering forced conversations about what questions the group actually wanted to explore. Meaningful frictions [preserve participants' agency](#). They provide opportunities for participants to intervene in AI processes, challenge outputs, and redirect conversations. We required collective rather than individual AI interaction specifically to preserve group agency over technological mediation. Moreover, meaningful frictions can [promote transparency](#). Friction points can make AI decision-making and rationale visible rather than hidden. Our "metabolism" approach, which showed how profiling, data retrieval, and response generation worked, created multiple opportunities for participant examination and critique. Additionally, meaningful frictions [provide the pauses necessary to prevent passive consumption of AI outputs](#). When our AI provided oversimplified responses or missed important perspectives, these limitations became discussion starters rather than process failures.

Design friction intentionally but distinguish it from mere technical dysfunction. Not every glitch serves democratic purposes. Technical failures that simply frustrate participants without adding deliberative depth are unproductive irritations that need addressing, not embracing. The task is to distinguish between the kinds of frictions and design in the ones that meaningfully enhance democratic exchange.

Step 4: Design for Collective Interaction with AI

Most AI systems optimize for individual user experience, but democratic exchange processes require collective interaction and engagement. Design AI integration that catalyses critical and democratically constructive group interaction with technology.

We required participants to collectively craft single prompts rather than allowing individual queries. This seemingly inefficient approach forced deliberation about what questions to ask, how to frame them, which information sources to prioritize. The collective prompt engineering process became as valuable as the AI responses themselves.

Consider how your AI integration might require rather than simply accommodate collective interaction:

Collective prompting: Require groups to negotiate shared questions rather than enabling individual queries. This forces conversation about values, assumptions, and information needs.

Shared outputs: Generate responses that the entire group must collectively evaluate rather than personalized recommendations that individuals can accept or reject privately.

Transparent profiling: If using any form of participant categorization, make it explicit and collectively discussable and contestable rather than hidden and individualized.

Group intervention points: Create opportunities for collective decisions about how AI should behave, what information to prioritize, how to interpret outputs.

Productive Derailment: While challenging to facilitate, create and accept moments when democratically constructive insights and/or participants' questions or critiques emerge and require the process to change course. When single individuals in our Dublin workshop brought up questions which were important to practicing and effectuating the democratic goods we were working towards, but which would shift the trajectory of the set process if we took them on, we let the workshop swerve. We used our [facilitative techniques](#) to integrate the new questions into an adapted process which refreshed and reinforced the democratic character of our democratic exchange.

This approach deliberately introduces inefficiency—it takes longer and feels more awkward than seamless individual interaction. But these inefficiencies serve democratic purposes by preserving collective agency over technological biases and mediation.

Step 5: Integrate Analog and Digital Thoughtfully

The most effective AI-embedded democratic processes don't rely entirely on digital interaction. Weave in analogue components that serve functions AI cannot: embodied discussion, spontaneous conversation direction, physical manipulation of ideas.

In our process, we deliberately used analogue methods for final validation and reflection: paper-based activities, face-to-face discussion, physical movement around the room. These analogue components weren't technological failures but design choices that preserved important democratic capacities.

Consider which aspects of your process benefit from analogue interaction:

Values clarification: Physical activities, conversational check-ins, written reflection that don't require technological mediation.

Spontaneous direction changes: Unscripted conversations that can redirect focus based on what emerges in the room.

Embodied deliberation: Discussion formats that use physical space, movement, gesture to support reasoning.

Final validation: Collective assessment processes that don't depend on technological interface.

The goal isn't to minimize technology but to use it where it is fit-for-purpose; where it serves specific democratic functions while preserving analogue capacities that technology cannot or, at least – seemingly should not, replace.

Step 6: Plan for Iterative Learning and Adaptation

AI-embedded democratic processes require ongoing adaptation based on what you learn through implementation. Design with the expectation that your first attempt will be imperfect and that these imperfections can become valuable learning opportunities.

Our experience across four different contexts, with three different types of participants – citizens, policymakers, technologists – revealed how the same process architecture functioned differently depending on participant expectations and comfort levels. Citizens focused on privacy and algorithmic categorization concerns. Policymakers examined governance implications. Technologists questioned technical implementation details.

Build learning and adaptation into your process design:

Regular reflection points: Structured opportunities for participants to comment on both substance and process

Flexible facilitation: Facilitator capacity to adapt based on what emerges rather than rigidly following predetermined scripts

Documentation approach: Methods for capturing both intended and unintended learning from process implementation

Iteration framework: Structure for incorporating participant feedback into future process iterations

Plan for substantial revisions based on what you learn, while being realistic about which changes are possible within your resource and timeline constraints.

SIGNS OF EFFECTIVE PROCESS DESIGN

- Participants understand how AI functions within the broader process and can articulate why they do or don't trust specific interactions.
- Participants feel more capable of engaging with complex topics collectively, not more dependent on technological mediation for individual understanding.
- The AI creates opportunities for meaningful disagreement rather than eliminating it. Participants can challenge both the substance and the technological mediation of their discussions.
- Friction points become learning opportunities rather than process obstacles.
- The process enhances rather than replaces human judgment. Participants maintain agency over collective reasoning while understanding how AI augments rather than determines their deliberative capacity.
- Most importantly, the technology serves the democratic exchange rather than directing it. Participants control how AI shapes their collective work, feeling empowered rather than controlled or hemmed-in by the technology and its integration into the democratic exchange process.

Facilitate an Effective AI-Embedded Democratic Exchange

OUTCOME: A democratic process that leverages AI as a catalyst for deeper deliberation rather than a substitute for human judgment

When facilitating a democratic exchange that includes AI, you're orchestrating something more complex than either traditional facilitation or straightforward technology on-boarding. The challenge lies in creating space for both meaningful engagement with the democratic substance and critical reflection on the AI's role, often simultaneously. This requires embracing the productive tension between efficiency and deliberation; between the desire for seamless technology and the democratic value of constructive friction.

The most critical insight from our experience with the Digital Democracy Lab is this: AI-embedded democratic exchange succeeds or fails based on facilitation choices, not technology features. The AI becomes democratically valuable only when skilled facilitation transforms its limitations, glitches, and apparent failures into opportunities for deeper democratic engagement.

NOTE: As with the other recipes and insights presented in this handbook, it is important to note that they are derived from the lessons learned through our work on the [Digital Democracy Lab](#) (DDL), an experimental deliberative process, and the [Digital Democracy Demonstrator](#) (DDD), an AI platform intended to experiment with augmentation and enhancement of democratic exchange. With this in mind, we will use the Demonstrator (DDD) and Lab (DDL) as reference points in the following recipe in order to help illustrate and clarify what we mean. We do not suggest that you need to replicate or adopt these exact tools. Rather, understanding how these systems were designed and used in practice can help inform your own design and development processes.

The DDL and DDD were developed within the KT4D project by an interdisciplinary team of democratic practitioners, designers, technologists and researchers. This collaboration enabled us to test AI integration in a live, facilitated deliberative setting, with real participants—including citizens, policymakers, civil society actors and technical experts.

WHAT YOU'LL NEED

To prepare to facilitate:

- Deep understanding of your democratic process goals (beyond what AI might accomplish). Return to your intended Democratic Goods to guide your facilitation decisions.
- Comfort with not knowing exactly how AI will behave during the session
- Multiple facilitation scenarios prepared for when technology doesn't work as expected
- Framework for distinguishing meaningful frictions from unproductive technical failure

To manoeuvre and navigate the AI element:

- Strategy for making AI decision-making and rationale visible and contestable during the process
- Plan for collective rather than individual interaction with AI systems
- Approach to AI outputs as conversation starters rather than authoritative solutions
- Method for handling AI errors, biases, or nonsensical responses constructively
- Process for iterative refinement based on participant feedback about AI interaction

To prepare and support participants:

- Activities that build critical digital literacy without requiring technical expertise
- Accessibility accommodations for participants with varying comfort levels with technology
- Set clear expectations about what AI can and cannot do in your specific context
- Framework for collective decision-making about how to use AI tools
- Support for participants who may find AI interaction alienating or disempowering

To maintain democratic quality:

- Commitment to slowing down rather than speeding up when AI is involved
- Process for ensuring AI enhances rather than replaces human agency
- Method for keeping democratic goods central even when technology becomes the focus
- Strategy for productive disagreement about both substance and AI's role
- Plan for meaningful contestation of AI processes and outputs

PREPARATION

Step 1: Design for Democratic Friction, Not Technological Smoothness

Meaningful frictions serve democratic purposes better than seamless AI interaction. Your role as facilitator involves deliberately introducing pauses, questions, and complications – and adaptively responding to such expected and unexpected glitches and disruptions – in ways that invite collective reflection on both the topic and the technology.

Plan specific moments where participants must slow down to examine how the AI works. In our experience, the most valuable discussions emerged when participants could see the AI's limitations: its biased data sources, oversimplified profiles, or overly-confident claims based on thin evidence. These apparent failures became teaching moments about algorithmic decision-making and democratic values.

Design collective rather than individual AI interaction. Require participants to negotiate together about what questions to ask the AI, which data sources to prioritize, and how to interpret outputs. This collective negotiation often produces more valuable democratic discussion than the AI's actual responses.

Consider which inefficiencies serve democratic purposes. The extended conversation about how to phrase a collective prompt, the debate over whether to trust certain data sources, the confusion about algorithmic categorization; Each of these are slowdowns that can create space for the kind of deliberation and contestation that effective democratic exchange requires.

Step 2: Prepare for Multiple Facilitation Realities

AI introduces unpredictability that requires facilitation agility. Technical failures, unexpected AI responses, and participant reactions you haven't anticipated will happen. Prepare for these scenarios as features rather than bugs of the process.

Develop facilitation paths for when technology doesn't work. What happens if the AI goes offline? If responses are nonsensical? If participants reject the profiling system entirely? Have contingent activities ready that can work without AI while still advancing your democratic goals.

Plan for radically different participant engagement levels. Some participants will be excited about AI possibilities; others will be sceptical or concerned. Some will want to dive deep into technical details; others will want to focus entirely on democratic substance. Design processes that honour all orientations.

Prepare responses to common AI concerns that serve democratic rather than technological purposes. When participants worry about bias, privacy, or algorithmic manipulation, frame these as opportunities to discuss what democracy requires from any information and decision-making system, not just AI.

Create time buffers for processing complexity. AI adds layers of complexity to democratic processes. Participants need time to understand not just the topic but also how AI is shaping their collective reasoning about it.

Step 3: Frame AI as a Boundary Object, Not an Oracle

Position AI explicitly as something to be examined and critiqued rather than trusted and utilized. This framing shapes how participants engage with both the technology and the democratic substance.

Introduce AI's role as experimental and limited rather than authoritative. Be honest about what your specific AI system can and cannot do, what compromises you made in its design, and what questions remain unanswered about its impact on democratic processes.

Make AI decision-making visible throughout the process. When the AI generates profiles, show participants how those profiles were created. When it produces policy recommendations, ensure participants can examine the data sources and reasoning. When it makes errors, use those errors as learning opportunities.

Encourage scepticism as a democratic skill. Productive doubt about AI outputs teaches participants to think critically about all information sources and decision-making processes, not just technological ones.

Position AI outputs as conversation starters rather than solutions. Frame AI-generated content as "one perspective" or "a starting point for discussion" rather than unequivocal expert analysis or neutral synthesis.

Step 4: Orchestrate Iterative Engagement Loops

Design your process around cycles of interaction, critique, and refinement rather than linear progression from AI input to human decision. These cycles build both democratic and digital literacy.

Create structured opportunities for participants to critique AI behaviour and suggest improvements. After participants interact with the AI, bring them together to discuss what worked, what didn't, and how the system might be changed to better serve democratic purposes.

Plan for participants to adjust their use of AI based on what they learn. If they discover bias in data sources, can they choose different sources? If they find the profiling system limiting, can they discuss its assumptions and constraints? If outputs feel inadequate, can they collectively refine their approach?

Design reflection points that connect AI critique to broader democratic questions. What does this AI's approach to profiling teach us about how democracy should handle diversity? What do its data source limitations tell us about expertise and inclusion in policy-making? How do its errors illuminate the challenges of collective decision-making?

Expect and plan for perspective shifts. Participants' views on both the substantive topic and AI's role will evolve during the process. Build in opportunities to capture and discuss these changes rather than assuming static positions.

Step 5: Balance Structure with Adaptability

AI-embedded democratic processes require more structure than traditional facilitation but also more flexibility to respond to unexpected developments.

Develop detailed facilitation guides while maintaining modularity (see Appendices C-G). Know exactly what you want to accomplish in each segment, but be ready to adjust based on participant needs, technical realities, and emerging insights.

Create clear learning objectives for both democratic content and AI interaction. Participants should leave understanding more about the policy topic and about AI's role in democratic processes. Design activities that advance both goals simultaneously.

Plan cultural and contextual adaptations. Our experience across different European contexts showed that the same basic process needed significant modification based on participants' relationships to technology, government, and democratic institutions.

Prepare for real-time adaptation based on group dynamics. Some groups will be more technically curious; others more focused on democratic concerns. Some will embrace experimentation; others will want clearly defined boundaries. Read your group and adjust accordingly.

Build in explicit check-ins about both process and content. Regularly ask participants what they're learning about the topic, what they're discovering about AI, and how the integration of the two is affecting their thinking.

Step 6: Cultivate Critical Digital Literacy Through Democratic Practice

Use the democratic process itself to teach critical thinking about AI rather than requiring technical expertise as a prerequisite.

Design activities that reveal AI assumptions through collective examination. Rather than explaining how algorithms work, create opportunities for participants to discover bias, limitations, and design choices through their own interaction with the system.

Frame technical literacy as civic literacy. Understanding AI becomes important not because participants need to become technologists, but because they need to be informed citizens who can shape how these tools are used in democratic contexts.

Use AI's errors and limitations as teaching opportunities. When the AI produces oversimplified profiles, generates biased outputs, or makes confident claims based on limited data, turn these moments into discussions about algorithmic decision-making and democratic values.

Connect specific AI behaviours to broader democratic principles. What do algorithmic categorization systems teach us about inclusion and representation? What do AI training datasets reveal about whose knowledge counts? How do AI outputs illuminate the challenges of collective sense-making?

SIGNS OF EFFECTIVE PROCESS FACILITATION

- Participants can articulate both what they learned about the topic and what they discovered about AI's role in democratic processes. They understand AI limitations and can critique algorithmic decision-making, not just accept or reject it wholesale.
- The group maintains agency over how AI shapes their collective reasoning. Participants feel empowered to adjust, critique, and direct AI interaction rather than feeling subject to algorithmic manipulation.
- AI enhances rather than replaces human deliberation. Technology creates opportunities for more informed discussion rather than eliminating the need for human judgment.
- Productive disagreement emerges about both substance and process. Participants engage in meaningful conflict about policy questions and about appropriate uses of AI in democratic contexts.
- The process generates learning that transfers beyond this specific AI system. Participants develop critical thinking skills they can apply to other technological tools and democratic processes.
- Most importantly, democratic goods remain central despite technological opportunity and complexity. The presence of AI should not diminish attention to inclusion, deliberation, accountability, and collective agency; instead, it must create new opportunities to examine and strengthen these democratic foundations.

FURTHER MATERIALS

For further inspiration you can peruse our own facilitation guides that we used during our different Use Cases.

In [Appendix C: Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Brussels](#) you will find our facilitation guide working specifically with policy makers and civil society organizations.

In [Appendix D: Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Krakow](#) as well as in [Appendix E : Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Madrid](#), you will find the facilitation guides we designed with a focus on deliberating with citizens.

In [Appendix F: Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Dublin](#) we have designed a facilitation guide specifically geared towards technologists and tech researchers.

All facilitation guides were based on [Appendix G: Service Blueprint for the Digital Democracy Lab](#) which was the foundational service design for all the Use Cases.

4 Get Going:

Keep learning, improving,
and evolving how you engage with technology

Some (hopefully useful) reflections, questions, and tips to keep in mind while working with AI—and other emerging technologies—as a democratic practitioner.

Reflections on Process

A. Making Decisions About AI

- Trust your democratic expertise. You understand what makes collective reasoning work, what builds trust, what enables meaningful participation. Don't let enthusiasm for technological possibility override that knowledge.
- Pressure to adopt AI quickly is common but rarely serves democratic purposes. Democratic processes require time for thoughtful consideration. Resist artificial deadlines that force hasty decisions about fundamental questions.
- "No" often represents the most democratic answer. Declining AI opportunities that don't clearly serve democratic goods is an act of stewardship and effective problem solving, i.e., defining and incorporating genuinely fit-for-purpose solutions. It is not technological backwardness.

B. Designing Effective AI

1. Key Insights from Our Own Design, Development, and Deployment

- The effectiveness of democratic AI emerges from its integration within broader deliberative contexts rather than from the technology alone. Our Demonstrator worked most successfully when positioned in three specific ways, despite—and sometimes because of—its limitations:
 - [As a conversation catalyst](#) - utilizing meaningful friction that encourages deliberation and challenges assumptions rather than providing seamless answers. Many of our best friction points emerged from resource constraints rather than design choices.
 - [As a tool for co-creating prompts](#) - requiring participants to deliberate, debate, and define key questions driving discussion rather than focusing on pre-set solutions or individual queries. The limitations of our system made collective interaction necessary rather than optional.
 - [As an analysis enricher](#) - drawing upon democratically selected, diverse sources to support collective reasoning rather than replacing human judgment. Our small dataset made the curation process visible and discussable in ways that vast datasets couldn't.
- Based on deployment learnings and honest assessment of our limitations, we would argue that [use of AI within democratic exchange is most effective and should be structured to enhance the qualities of the exchange \(deliberative, participatory, contestational, etc.\) rather than determine solutions. This means moving from policy outputs to discussion inputs by framing outputs as questions rather than proposals, showing relative alignments instead of fixed profiles, and responding to perspective shifts during deliberation.](#)

2. Other Notes on Process

- Designing and building AI for democratic exchange is different from building commercial AI. In some cases, it may require the active un-building of an already built AI in order to effectively retrofit it for democratic purposes. Moreover, the iterative co-design process, the transparency requirements, the need for participant testing, and the legal compliance issues all create different constraints and opportunities which can impact the budget and timeline in ways that are different from developing commercial AI. Keep this in mind and plan accordingly.
- Expect tension between democratic values, technical constraints, and resource limitations. Current commercial AI technologies aren't designed for transparency or democratic input, and proper implementation is expensive. Working within these constraints requires creative workarounds, honest communication about compromises, and sometimes designing imperfect tools which can serve democratic purposes more effectively than polished ones.

- Don't let technical sophistication overshadow democratic purpose, but also don't let budget or timing constraints undermine core democratic principles. The most advanced AI system isn't necessarily the most democratically valuable one, but the cheapest approach isn't necessarily democratic either. Sometimes simpler systems that participants can fully understand serve democratic purposes better than sophisticated ones that remain mysterious.
- Consider keeping the system in "perpetual beta" rather than pursuing a finalized product. Our experience showed that the Demonstrator's value emerged from its role as a research-through-design artifact that could evolve based on democratic input rather than a polished tool optimized for user satisfaction. Embrace the experimental nature and learn from the inevitable glitches and errors.

C. Designing Democratically Effective AI-Embedded Exchange Processes

- Process architecture matters more than technological sophistication. Simple AI systems that participants can fully understand often serve democratic purposes better than advanced systems that remain mysterious.
- Imperfection can be democratically valuable. Technical limitations that make AI decision-making visible and contestable often enhance democratic engagement more than polished performance would.
- Integration requires democratic expertise, not just technical capacity. The most sophisticated AI becomes meaningless without careful attention to how it affects participants' capacities to constructively reason, reflect, relate, disagree, and debate within a democratic exchange process.
- The goal isn't just building better AI but creating better conditions for good-faith, critical and constructive democratic exchange to emerge.

D. Facilitating Democratically Effective AI-Embedded Exchange Processes

- The effectiveness of AI-embedded democratic exchange depends heavily on contextual factors: participant backgrounds, cultural attitudes toward technology and government, institutional settings, and facilitator expertise. The same basic process produces very different results depending on these variables.
- Facilitator skill matters more than AI sophistication. Groups with skilled facilitators who could navigate both democratic process and AI integration had productive experiences even when the technology was glitchy or limited.

- Meaningful frictions seem to create more democratic value than seamless efficiency. Participants learned most from moments when AI limitations were visible and discussable rather than when technology worked invisibly.
- Cultural attitudes toward data sources and authority significantly shape engagement. Participants in different contexts brought very different assumptions about the credibility of government sources, academic research, and media reporting that affected how they interacted with AI-curated information.
- Collective interaction with AI generates more democratic goods than individual use. Requiring participants to negotiate together about AI interaction created valuable deliberation about values, assumptions, and democratic priorities.

1. The Facilitation Paradox

- AI introduces a paradox for democratic facilitators. The technology promises to make processes more efficient, yet democratic goods often emerge from what appear to be inefficiencies: extended discussion, productive confusion, contested assumptions, and collective struggle with complexity.
- Your role becomes managing this tension constructively. When do you allow AI to speed up information processing, and when do you slow down to examine what that processing assumes? When do you embrace AI-generated insights, and when do you encourage scepticism about algorithmic reasoning? When do you let technology guide the conversation, and when do you reassert human control over the democratic process?
- The most democratically valuable AI integration happens when these tensions remain constructive rather than resolved. Participants learn most when they can experience both AI's capabilities and limitations, both its potential to deepen democratic exchange and its tendency to substitute someone else's (designer or developer's) algorithmic logic for the participants' own democratic judgment.

What We Learned: AI's Democratic Potential Is Narrower Than Assumed

Our experimental Digital Democracy Lab workshops across Brussels, Madrid, Krakow, and Dublin revealed several crucial insights about AI's actual rather than assumed democratic potential:

Imperfections Can Be More Valuable Than Perfection: The AI system's limitations, biases, and obvious flaws often produced more valuable democratic discussion than its successes. When participants could easily see and critique AI shortcomings, it sparked deeper conversations about expertise, authority, and decision-making. Conversely, polished AI performance tended to discourage critical engagement.

Transparency Must Be Designed, Not Assumed: Making AI decision-making visible and contestable required deliberate design choices that differed markedly from commercial AI experiences. This often meant making

systems more awkward and less efficient, but it enabled meaningful participant agency over technological mediation. Most commercial AI systems are designed to obscure rather than reveal their operation, making them fundamentally unsuitable for democratic contexts without significant adaptation.

Cultural Context Shapes Everything: The same AI system functioned completely differently across different contexts. In Krakow, participants distrusted government data sources and avoided them. In Madrid, they questioned newspaper reliability. In Brussels, policymakers brought different assumptions about academic versus policy sources. These differences became valuable parts of democratic conversation when made visible, but they also revealed the impossibility of creating culturally neutral AI systems.

Facilitation Determines Democratic Value: Even sophisticated AI became democratically meaningless without skilled facilitation that could transform technological interactions into opportunities for democratic learning. The technology itself was never sufficient; its democratic value depended entirely on how human facilitators framed, contextualized, and integrated AI interactions within broader democratic processes.

Collective Interaction Preserves Democratic Character: Requiring groups to negotiate shared prompts rather than enabling individual AI queries preserved collective agency over technological mediation and created natural space for values-based discussion about information needs and trust. Individual AI interaction, no matter how sophisticated, cannot replicate the democratic dynamics that emerge from collective negotiation.

Examples of Questions You Can (and maybe should) Ask

A. Making Decisions About AI

- Consider what problem AI is supposed to solve in this situation. Is this about improving democratic outcomes, reducing costs, appearing cutting-edge, addressing genuine participant needs, or something else entirely?
- Consider your participants as well. Will AI integration feel empowering or alienating? Will it enhance their sense of agency or undermine it? Will it catalyse critical thinking, apathy, or distrust?
- For any AI proposal, work through this fundamental question: *What would this do to the democratic character of our process?*
- What capacities would AI add? What human capacities would AI replace? What would be lost entirely?

B. Designing Effective AI

- Before considering any technical specifications, establish clear answers to: What democratic goods does your process aim to foster? What kinds of interactions do you want to enable? What should participants be able to do together that they couldn't do before?

- When checking in with technical partners, ask questions like:
 - To what extent are participants able to recognise the decisions the technology is attempting to afford for them and able to accept or decline those affordances according to their own, genuine preferences?
 - What assumptions about user behaviour are we building in?
 - Where might participants want or need more control over the process?
 - How can we make our limitations transparent and contestable?
 - What would break if participants used this differently than intended?
 - How can we make the limitations of our approach visible, discussable, and contestable? How might we explain our limitations without undermining the democratic purpose?
 - How do we ensure participants can understand how this works and what data and design-decisions it depends on?
 - How do participants evaluate the credibility and bias of information sources?
 - How do participants understand and critique the ways their own data is being collected and or used to shape the interaction/experience they are having?
 - What happens when the AI categories don't match how participants see themselves? How do we prevent this from reinforcing echo chambers?
- Consider how you might frame constraints honestly and explicitly: Where can we create visibility and give participants control? Where must we acknowledge – but not necessarily accept – limitations? How do we turn our constraints into democratic features?

C. Designing Democratically Effective AI-Embedded Exchange Processes

- As you design your own process, ask yourself:
 - *What kinds of democratic interaction does your process need to enable?*
 - *What should participants be able to do together that they couldn't accomplish individually or collectively without support from an AI tool?*
 - *How do you want people to relate to information, to each other, and to the collective engagement process itself?*

D. Facilitating Democratically Effective AI-Embedded Exchange Processes

- What happens if the AI goes offline? If responses are nonsensical? If participants reject the profiling system entirely? [Develop facilitation paths for when technology doesn't work.](#)
- How might you need to shift your facilitation approach if/when participants discover bias in data sources? Can they choose different sources if/when they find the system limiting? Can they discuss its assumptions and constraints if/when outputs feel inadequate? Can they collectively refine their approach? [Plan for participants to adjust their use of AI based on what they learn.](#)
- What does the AI's data source limitations or preferences tell participants about expertise and inclusion in policy-making? How do the AI's errors illuminate the challenges of collective decision-making? [Design reflection points that connect AI critique to broader democratic questions.](#)
- What do algorithmic categorization systems teach us about inclusion and representation? What do AI training datasets reveal about whose knowledge counts? How do AI outputs illuminate the challenges of collective sense-making? [Connect specific AI behaviours to broader democratic principles.](#)

Appendix A: The Digital Democracy Lab

Understand Our Digital Democracy Lab

The Digital Democracy Lab (DDL) is an experimental model of a mini-public which integrates AI in novel, exploratory ways. As a prototype, the DDL is neither a perfect representation of a mini public nor a seamless deployment of AI. However, it provides an ideal opportunity to investigate the added-value and risks such technology can afford, within the settings of democratic exchange.

In essence, the DDL was designed as a one-day workshop aimed at exploring and demonstrating the potential and limitations of AI and big data in enhancing democratic exchange processes. The Lab incorporates these technologies within established best practices for civic participation, creating a unique environment for understanding and evaluating AI's role in democratic processes.

The landing page of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator.

The Lab employs a systematic approach, beginning with addressing a wickedly complex and multifaceted challenge. For this first iteration of the DDL, the policy focus was on the EU's role in labour market transitions during the AI era. Participants engaged with the activities of the DDL and the Digital Democracy Demonstrator through its UX/UI (User Experience/User Interface) to understand the mechanics of large language models, explore training data, and examine how the user profiling is determined.

Through collaborative exercises, participants generated prompts for a specialised GPT model using a custom knowledge source of 30 documents—comprising 10 from newspapers, 10 from policy papers, and 10 from academic journals—leveraging the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) technique. Participants then critically reviewed the AI-generated policy papers and engaged in iterative improvement cycles to address any misalignment between their own expectations and values and the assumptions encoded in the specialised GPT regarding those expectations and values.

This section outlines the main workshop design, including a brief description of the development process, the DDL's structure, tools, and participant engagement processes, providing a narrative walkthrough of the facilitation guide used for Use Cases 2 and 3. The facilitation guide was specifically tailored for Use Cases 2 and 3, as these were directed towards citizens and citizen-facing civil society organisations (CSOs)—the usual participants of mini-publics. Use Cases 1 and 4 were subsequently adapted from this main facilitation guide to better suit the respective audiences of policymakers and software. A more detailed description of the objectives of each use case is provided below.

I. Description of the Digital Democracy Lab workshop flow

A. Setting the Stage

The workshop began with a session dedicated to "Setting the Stage." This phase aimed to introduce participants to the objectives of the DDL and provide them with foundational knowledge of AI and its implications for democratic processes.

Welcome and Introduction

Participants were greeted and invited to engage in a brief check-in activity, where they completed statements such as:

- "I trust AI to help me with _____ because _____."
- "I don't trust AI to help me with _____ because _____."

This exercise set the tone for collaborative discussion, highlighting individual perspectives on AI. Facilitators also provided a brief overview of the workshop agenda and objectives, ensuring participants understood the day's flow.

B. Contextual Presentation

An engaging presentation followed, introducing the intersection of democracy and AI. This included examples of AI applications in democratic settings, challenges such as transparency and bias, and the importance of democratic stewardship of AI tools. The presenter emphasised the unique role of the DDL in exploring these issues interactively.

Presentation held in Madrid, Spain on the 29th of October, 2024

C. Interactive Engagement with the Digital Democracy Demonstrator

The core of the workshop centred around the Digital Democracy Demonstrator (DDD), an AI-informed platform developed to support deliberative processes. Participants engaged with the platform through the following structured activities:

Profile Quiz

Participants began by completing a 30-question quiz on the DDD. This quiz assessed their perspectives on topics such as technology, societal systems, and economic priorities. Based on their responses, the system categorised them into one of eight personas, which served as a lens for generating policy outputs. The eight possible personas that were assessed using the profile matrix were: Market Proponent, Responsible Innovator, Technology Sceptic, Balanced Regulator, Technology Enthusiast, Social Impact Advocate, System Critic, and Worker Advocate.

Participants are asked to join the session which leads them to the profiling quiz

The participant answers 30 questions to assess their profile

At the end of the quiz, the participant received their profile

Exploring the AI Metabolism

Participants were introduced to the concept of the “metabolism”—the underlying processes that informed the DDL. This section of the DDL focused on:

- Exploring the data used to train the specialty GPT - how it was selected, and by whom;
- Learn how data was synthesised - using RAG (Retrieval-augmented generation)
- Understand the parameters (instructions) used to train model and how they were created, and by whom, including:
 - How the profiles were created, by whom, and how profiles were used to train GPT
- Understand the limitations and biases of parameters, profiles, and data selected, created, and relied up

The participants could peruse the metabolism through explainer videos and looking at specific data sources, always accompanied by hands-on discussions and activities within the Lab experience

This segment allowed participants to navigate the DDD’s interface, explore explainer videos, and examine data sources.

Explainer videos (this one describes how the user profiles were developed, by whom and through what criteria) served as additional support to understand the metabolism of the DDD

The data sources used to train the specialty GPT were shared with the participants through the DDD. Seeing the different data source groups, or “peer reviewed academic papers”, “policy documents” and “newspaper articles”, the participant could explore the sources themselves and also discuss the reliability of the sources. This was a hands-on activity conducted in pairs, fostering collaborative learning and critical reflection. Participants discussed questions such as:

- Are the data sources representative?
- What biases might exist in the profile creation or data selection processes?

Participants could then discuss what sources they wanted the specialty GPT to generate answers from

Prompt Engineering and AI Outputs

After understanding the metabolism, the participants navigated towards collaboratively drafting prompts they would find useful to better discuss the question of AI and the labour market. This section of the lab consisted of:

- Collaboratively drafting a prompt to use for GPT
- Selecting which source (Newspaper articles, Policy Papers, academic journals, or a mix of all three) to request GPT rely on.
- Witnessing the automated generation of a policy brief based on prompt, selected source, and “user profile” distribution in the room.

The prompt interface mimics other mainstream LLM interfaces

Crafting Prompts

Facilitators guided participants in collaboratively drafting prompts for the AI system. These prompts instructed the GPT to generate policy briefs tailored to the group's profile distribution. Example prompts included:

- “Generate a policy brief on AI and the EU Labour market, specifically focusing on job displacement and workers rights”.
- “Propose policies addressing the meaning of AI in Europe's overall economic growth.”

A collaboratively developed prompt is entered into the DDD and it generates an output

Generating and Reviewing Outputs

Using a shared display, participants observed the DDD generate a draft policy brief. Copies of the brief were printed and distributed for individual review. Participants used red pens to annotate the draft, focusing on two key questions:

- How well does the brief align with participants' expectations?
- What improvements could make the AI output more trustworthy?

Participants discussing the outputs of the DDD, in Krakow, Poland on the 25th of October 2024

D. Iterative Discussions and Refinements

Group Reflection

Participants reconvened to share their reviews, discussing the strengths and weaknesses of the AI-generated brief. They considered whether adjustments to prompts or data sources could yield better outputs.

Participants in Madrid discussing the outputs of the DDD

Second Iteration

Based on the group's feedback, facilitators input revised prompts into the DDD. The new output was reviewed and critiqued, emphasising how changes in prompt engineering impacted results.

Second iteration of prompt and DDD output

E. Closing Discussion

The workshop concluded with a plenary discussion, where participants reflected on their experiences and the implications of AI in democratic contexts. Key discussion points included:

- The trustworthiness of AI-generated outputs.
- Ethical considerations and risks.
- Potential applications and limitations of AI in policymaking.

This session provided facilitators with valuable feedback for refining the DDL and informed broader discussions on the integration of AI in democratic innovation.

Appendix B:

The Digital Democracy Demonstrator

Explore the Digital Democracy Demonstrator

The Digital Democracy Demonstrator (DDD) is a prototype AI platform developed within the KT4D project to explore how machine learning and large language models can be used to support—not replace—deliberative democratic processes. It was designed to work in tandem with facilitated, in-person workshops, providing participants with AI-generated outputs that surface multiple perspectives, contextual insights, and open-ended questions rooted in a curated knowledge base.

Rather than positioning the AI as a policy recommender, the DDD acts as a "neutral" conversation partner, aiming to prompt reflection and dialogue rather than prescribe solutions. It draws exclusively on a curated dataset of media articles, academic papers, and EU policy documents, using a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architecture to provide transparent, referenceable responses. You can access the DDD and supporting materials via the links below:

Demonstrator: <https://kt4d-ddl.azurewebsites.net/en>

GitHub: <https://github.com/HybridCore-dev/KT4D>

Appendix C: Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Brussels

Digital Democracy Lab | Democratic Stewardship of AI and AI in Democratic Innovation

Facilitation Guide | Use Case 1

Date: Tuesday, 15th October, 2024 | 10:00-12:30 + lunch and networking

Place: Press club, Brussels

Duration: 2.5 hours

Target Audience: Policymakers focused on democratic innovation, with some representation from AI and emerging technology policy experts

- AI HLEG
- European AI Alliance
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights
- European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
- DIGITAL SME Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence
- DIGITALEUROPE
- 42Artificial intelligence
- OECD AI Policy Observatory
- OECD
- Subcommittee on Human Rights (DROI)
- EU Parliamentary Committees on Civil Liberties

Workshop Objectives:

- **Explore** the integration of AI technologies in democratic processes
- **Discuss** the concept of "democracy-in-the-loop" and democratic stewardship of technology
- **Enrich** the policy Delphi study data with insights from democratic innovation and technology focused policymakers
- **Engage** with the Digital Democracy Demonstrator (DDD) as a boundary object

- **Develop** initial considerations and principles for:
 - AI integration in democratic exchange processes and
 - Democratic processes / practices integration in AI and other emerging technologies (Democratic stewardship and Democracy-in-the-loop Technologies)

Value Proposition:

The Digital Democracy Lab offers you a unique 2.5-hour workshop to explore the intersection of AI and democratic processes:

1. Gain insights from the latest policy Delphi study findings on AI governance approaches in democratic contexts.
2. Engage with the Digital Democracy Demonstrator as a design research prototype, exploring practical applications of AI in democratic innovation.
3. Contribute to developing initial guidelines and principles for "democracy-in-the-loop" AI applications and democratic stewardship of technology.
4. Participate in collaborative discussions to identify gaps in current AI governance approaches regarding democratic processes.
5. Help shape policy pathways for responsible AI integration in democratic innovation, considering both potential benefits and risks.
6. Network with peers from democratic innovation and AI policy backgrounds, fostering cross-disciplinary dialogue.

By participating, you'll have the opportunity to influence the development of benchmarks and principles for AI integration in democratic exchange processes. This workshop offers a stimulating environment to apply your expertise in democratic innovation to critical questions of AI governance or expertise in AI and technology to questions of integrating emerging tech in democratic processes, helping to ensure that technological advancements align with and enhance democratic values and practices.

DIGITAL DEMOCRACY LAB - USE CASE 2 & 3					
Time	Activity	Goal/s	Duration	Structure + Notes + Facilitator(s)	Technical Notes
09:00	Set Up	To ensure we are adequately prepared and materials are organised for an optimal participant experience.	60 minutes	<p><i>[Name Person]</i> arrive at site to set up and ensure everything is in place.</p> <p>-----</p> <p>https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1PMI9f1dh8KQimtewtmuemCn6wCPfvTqZ/edit?usp=sharing&oid=117972433158693350287&rtpof=true&sd=true</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Projector for presentations <input type="checkbox"/> Flipcharts or digital whiteboards for group discussions <input type="checkbox"/> Handouts summarising key Delphi survey findings and policy pathways? <input type="checkbox"/> Handouts summarising Democracy-in-the-loop and democratic governance? <input type="checkbox"/> Template handouts for creating initial guidelines for democracy-in-the-loop applications
10:00	Welcome and Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome participants Brief introductions from participants 	5 minutes	<p><i>[Name Person]</i> offers a formal welcome, introduces himself and the other facilitators and asks each participant to introduce themselves by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Their name; Their role; What they're currently focused most on; and Their initial thoughts about AI as part of democratic processes summarised in 3 words or less. 	
10:05		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview of workshop objectives and agenda 	5 minutes	<p><i>[Name Person]</i> provides introductory statements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome to the Digital Democracy Lab 	

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Digital Democracy Lab is a unique opportunity to explore the intersection of artificial intelligence (AI) and democratic processes. • The goal of the workshop is to map pathways for responsibly utilising AI as part of deliberative processes and identify gaps in current AI governance approaches regarding democratic processes. • A Digital Democracy prototype tool - called the Digital Democracy Demonstrator will be presented to elicit feedback on initial guidelines for democracy-in-the-loop AI applications and democratic stewardship of technology. • As a participant, you can help shape policy pathways for responsible integration of AI in democratic processes, considering both potential benefits and risks. 	
10:10			5 minutes	<p>[Name Person] walks through the agenda of the day:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and introductions (15m) • Setting the scene: AI & Democratic Innovation (15m) • Engaging with the Digital Democracy Demonstrator (30m) • Break (10m) • Deepening the discussion (50m) • Critical reflections (20m) • Closing & next steps (10m) 	
10:15	Setting the Scene: AI and Democratic Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation on the intersections of AI and democratic processes • Introduction to the concept of "democracy-in-the-loop" and democratic 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Person] offers a high level summary of the Delphi and uses the opportunity to bring the focus to current AI governance approaches regarding democratic processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There seems to be decent interest in exploring how these technologies should be integrated into democratic processes / practices, but there seems to be uncertainty - and some pessimism - about how to do so in ways that are functionally effective and ethically appropriate. 	
10:20			10+ minutes	<p>[Name Person] provides an accessible introduction about intersections of democracy and AI.</p>	

10:30		stewardship of technology		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers introduction to “democracy-in-the-loop” and democratic stewardship of technology as useful approaches to integrate AI (and other technologies) into democratic processes and practices in ways that are functionally effective and ethically appropriate. 	
			15 minutes	<p>[Name Person] take and respond to questions</p> <p>If time remaining, [Name Person] ask participants to discuss pertinent questions with their neighbours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questions can be sourced from the presentations 	
			5 minutes	<p>[Name Person] offers a brief synthesis of the key components of [Presenters] presentation and discussion in order to provide emphasis and to use the synthesis to segway into the next exercise (Engaging with the Digital Democracy Demonstrator) and re-introduce [Name Person] to lead it.</p>	
10:55	Engaging with the Digital Democracy Demonstrator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to the Digital Democracy Demonstrator and its purpose as a boundary object Guided exploration of the demonstrator's features World Cafe with four tables, each focused on: Challenges and 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Person] uses a laptop connected to a projector to share the unique steps for using the digital democracy demonstrator.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>The purpose here is not for the participants to use the Demonstrator, but - rather - for the participants to gain enough exposure and experience with the Demonstrator so they can understand:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>What the Demonstrator is, i.e., what it is meant to do;</i> <i>How it works; and</i> <i>Why it works that way based on the parameters and inputs that have been used to develop it.</i> 	[Name Person] can use the streamlined version of the DDD in order to showcase the DDD process without needing to go through the entire thing
11:05			15 minutes	<p>Once [Name Person] completes the walk through of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator, [Name Person] can hand off to [Name Person] to introduce the next part of the exercise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “We have 4 tables set up” “Please divide yourselves evenly across all four.” “Can I get one volunteer from each table to be a note taker?” → “Each of your tables will focus on the following question: 	<input type="checkbox"/> Need 4 tables with markers and parchment paper with the central question written on the middle with mind-map lines leading off from it.

11:20		considerations when integrating AI into democratic processes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Given what you already know, what you heard from [Presenter] earlier, and what you just saw using the Digital Democracy Demonstrator, what are the challenges and considerations to bear in mind when integrating AI into democratic processes? 	[Name Person] should circulate amongst the tables confirming participants know what to do and that note takers are compiling the discussion in written form on the parchment paper.
				5 minutes	<p>At 11:20, [Name Person] warns the participants that they have 5 minutes remaining.</p> <p>At 11:24, [Name Person] warns the participants that they have 1 minute remaining.</p> <p>At 11:25, [Name Person] thanks the groups and dismisses them for a 10 minute break.</p>
11:25	Break	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide participants with a chance to pause and mingle Provide opportunity for facilitators to game plan for final 30 minutes 	10 minutes		<p>During this time, [Name Person] convene to discuss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If any changes should be made for remainder of lab; and How to most appropriately incorporate insights from the first hour into the next set of discussions and activities.
11:35	Deepening the Discussion:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants collaborate to draft some initial 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Person] welcomes everyone back and introduces the next exercise:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The next exercise will build on our previous small group and collective thinking. 	If the participants don't seem able to self-organise into groups of three, [Name Person]

11:45 12:00	AI Governance in Democratic Contexts	guidelines for “democracy-in-the-loop” AI applications.		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. For the next 30 minutes, we will work in groups of 3 to draft some initial guidelines for “democracy-in-the-loop” AI applications. 3. To do this, each group will be provided with a worksheet you can use which will help you lay out and compile what you and your collaborators believe are the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Goal: _____ ○ Challenges: _____, _____, _____. ○ Initial Guidelines <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. _____ ii. _____ iii. _____ iv. _____ v. _____ 4. As you work to craft these initial guidelines, it may be helpful to consider the following questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What is the technology trying to solve? ○ What parts of democratic exchange is it substituting? ○ What do we win/lose by using the AI boundary object (the demonstrator)? 	can create clusters. It would be ideal if each group could include at least one policymaker expert on technology.
			15 minutes	Participants commence and work in their small groups.	
			5 minutes	<p>At 12:00, [Name Person] warns the participants that they have 5 minutes remaining.</p> <p>At 12:04, [Name Person] warns the participants that they have 1 minute remaining.</p> <p>At 12:05, [Name Person] thanks the groups, asks them to rejoin the plenary circle, hands off facilitation to [Name Person] and collects each groups’ worksheet.</p>	

12:05	Critical Reflection: Implications and Way Forward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plenary discussions on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Initial guideline shareback ○ Forward looking guidelines and recommendations. ○ Strategies for ensuring democratic stewardship of AI technologies ○ Policy recommendations / guideline iterations for responsible AI integration in democratic innovation 	18 minutes	<p>[Name Person] facilitates a plenary discussion in which:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One representative from each group offers a shareback of the initial guidelines they created. ● With consideration for the guidelines, XXX prompts the group to discuss the following topics one at a time: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Potential risks and unintended consequences of AI in democratic processes; 2. Strategies for ensuring democratic stewardship of AI technologies, above and beyond their use in democratic processes; 3. Policy recommendations - or iterations to their initial guidelines - for responsible AI integration in democratic innovation. 	
12:23			2 minutes	<p>As the conversation winds down, [Name Person] wraps up the plenary discussion by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thanking everyone for sharing their perspectives; 2. Having the Demos Note taker share back a synthesis of the key insights from the discussion; and 3. Handing off to [Name Person] to close out the Digital Democracy Lab 	
12:25	Closing and Next Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recap of key takeaways ● Information on 	~5 minutes	<p>[Name Person] offers:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A closing synthesis of the day's discussions; 2. Information on what's to come with the KT4D project; and a 3. An invitation to stay involved in this work (KT4D, specifically, and 	<p>Note takers from throughout the day can contribute to the synthesis of the day's insights and take aways.</p>

		<p>how insights will inform further research and policy development and invitation to collaborate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Information on follow-up activities and opportunities for continued engagement		Democratic stewardship of AI technologies, more generally).	
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Appendix D: Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Krakow

Digital Democracy Lab | Democratic Stewardship of AI Enabled Democratic Decisions

Facilitation Guide | Use Case 2 & 3

Dates: Friday, 25 October, 2024 (Krakow) | Tuesday, 29 October, 2024 (Madrid)

Place:

Duration: 5 hours (4 hours + 1 hour lunch)

Target Audience: Citizens and CSOs

Workshop Objectives:

- **Develop critical digital literacy:** Enhance participants' understanding of AI systems used in democratic deliberation and policy-making contexts, including exploring the "metabolism" of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator and AI systems more generally.
- **Practise democratic stewardship:** Provide hands-on experience in generating, reviewing, and revising AI-produced materials, demonstrating the concept of democracy-in-the-loop and democratic stewardship of technology.
- **Evaluate AI in democracy:** Encourage reflection on the trustworthiness, legitimacy, and potential impacts of using AI in democratic and policy-making processes, including discussion of risks, benefits, and ethical considerations.

- **Identify improvements and implications:** Explore potential enhancements, limitations, and broader implications of AI-enabled democratic deliberation and policy creation processes.
- **Gather insights for future development:** Collect participant feedback on their experience with the AI system and overall process to inform future iterations of the Digital Democracy Lab and contribute to the broader KT4D project.

Value Proposition:

The Digital Democracy Lab offers you a hands-on opportunity to explore the intersection of AI and democratic decision-making. In this 5-hour workshop (including a 1-hour lunch), you'll:

1. Develop critical digital literacy by examining the inner-workings and design decisions of AI systems, generally, and AI systems used in democratic deliberation and policy-making, more specifically.
2. Gain practical experience in democratic stewardship of technology by generating, reviewing, and revising AI-produced policy briefs.
3. Evaluate the trustworthiness and legitimacy of AI in democratic processes through direct interaction with a specialised AI system.
4. Contribute to improving AI-enabled democratic deliberation by providing feedback on your experience and identifying potential enhancements.
5. Engage in meaningful discussions about the ethical considerations, risks, and benefits of integrating AI into policy-making.
6. Enhance your ability to participate in future public debates on AI governance by understanding both its potential and limitations.

By participating, you'll play an active role in shaping how AI could be responsibly integrated into democratic processes - and how democratic stewardship can be integrated into new technologies -, ensuring that future implementations align with citizens' values and expectations.

DIGITAL DEMOCRACY LAB - USE CASE 2 & 3					
Time	Activity	Goal/s	Duration	Structure + Notes + Facilitator(s)	Technical Notes
	Set Up	To ensure we are adequately prepared and materials are organised for an optimal participant experience.	60-90 minutes	<i>[Name Facilitator(s)] arrive at site to set up and ensure everything is in place.</i> -----	<input type="checkbox"/> Tablets / laptops / stationary computers are set up and have the Digital Democracy Demonstrator loaded <input type="checkbox"/> Projector is set up <input type="checkbox"/> Printer is linked, set up, and full of paper <input type="checkbox"/> Red pens and other workshop tools are compiled <input type="checkbox"/> Chairs are grouped in a circular shape for initial plenary
10:00	Gather and welcome	Participant Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcomed to the lab • Introduce themselves to each other + complete check in questions • Receive an overview of day's agenda 	10 minutes	<i>[Name Facilitator(s)]</i> introduces themselves and <i>- [Name Facilitator(s)]</i> . Together, they invite all participants to introduce themselves and respond to the check in question/ playful self-assessment of critical digital literacy. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fill in the blanks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ I trust AI to help me with _____ because _____ ○ I don't trust AI to help me with _____ because _____ 	
			5 minutes	<i>[Name Facilitator(s)]</i> offers a formal welcome and some short introductory statements. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to include a framing which situates participants within an 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Become intellectually prepared to begin tasks of Lab</i> 		<p>“imaginary” use case, in which their local municipality is considering using the Digital Democracy Lab to make specific policy decisions. In this case, the municipality is exploring policy related to Labour Policy and AI. So, we are asking participants to engage in the Lab from this perspective, so we can explore not whether this technology and/or forum is “good” or “bad”, but to explore the ways by which a technology such as this and a forum which affords democratic stewardship can affect democratic decision making processes and afford effective and helpful democracy-in-the-loop technologies.</p>	
			10 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] provides an accessible introduction about intersections of democracy and AI.</p>	
			5 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] provides participants with a briefing about the primary set of tasks they will conduct as part of the Digital Democracy Lab:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To critically engage with - and democratically steward - an AI supported process for creating and revising speculative EU Labor policy. • While we will use EU Labour Policy and the integration of AI as a focal point for our conversation, we just want to emphasise that the real purpose of our Lab is for us to experience, and as we said, critically engage and explore how we can democratically steward an AI in this process. 	
10:30	Profile Quiz	<p>Participant Experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Understand the purpose and value of providing their positionality regarding AI, Economy, and current system/s</i> 	5 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] introduces the quiz which participants will take.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The following 30-question quiz explores your views on technology, societal systems, and economic priorities. It covers topics from automation to wealth redistribution. Your answers will help gauge which policy positions you might support or oppose, providing insights into your perspective on key modern issues alongside other participants. • Answer each question based on your genuine beliefs, not what you think is "correct" or socially acceptable. There are no right or wrong responses. You'll be placed into one of eight personas representing 	<p>The quiz</p> <p>Facilitators need to “Create the session” and complete the quiz themselves in order for the process to work. Participants should “join the session”.</p>

		<p>structures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand and - to the extent possible enjoy - the process of responding to quiz questions and sharing positionality. • Provide facilitators insight the particular positionality they have 		<p>different views on technology, society, and economics. The Demonstrator will then generate a policy brief aligned with all participants' perspectives.”</p>	
			15 minutes	<p>Each participant - using a provided tablet, laptop, or their own phone - completes the initial profile quiz on the Digital Democracy Demonstrator.</p> <p>Once all participants have completed the quiz, [Name Facilitator(s)] introduces the next steps</p>	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] should move from participant to participant to ensure they are following the processes and understand how to complete the quiz.</p>
10:50	Understand the AI Metabolism / Recipe	<p>Participant Experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore the data used to train the specialty GPT - how it was selected, and by whom • Learn how data was synthesised - using RAG (Retrieval-augmented generation) • Understand the parameters (instructions) used to train 	5 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] clarifies (1) the use of the quiz results, (2) provides an orientation to participants for how to navigate the opportunity to understand the AI’s metabolism / recipe for producing the output they will engage with later in the workshop, and (3) encourages participants to explore the metabolism in an in-depth way.</p> <p>(1) Your results on the Digital Democracy Demonstrator are not necessarily indicative of your entire perspective regarding technology, societal systems, and economic priorities; But, it does offer some insight into the kinds of ideas, opportunities, or policies you might find most exciting.. or concerning.</p> <p>The way the Digital Democracy Demonstrator works is that it will consider your profile and the other profiles in the room. It will consider these profiles as lenses as it uses an automated approach called Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to sort through source materials from newspapers across Europe, academic papers, and policy papers on the topics of AI and labour policy to generate a policy brief - i.e., a proposal for the kind of policy the EU should enact</p>	

		<p>model and how they were created, and by whom, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How the profiles were created, by whom, and how profiles were used to train GPT ● Understand the limitations and biases of parameters, profiles, and data selected, created, and relied up 		<p>on the topic.</p> <p>The policy brief that the Demonstrator will generate will pull together cited sentences or sections from across all the sources which - based on how the Demonstrator’s parameters were set - it calculates should align most effectively with the values and expectations of each of you - i.e., the different profiles - in the room.</p> <p>(2) In order to help you understand how all of this happening and offer you more opportunity to critically engage with the Demonstrator system, you will now take some time to explore the inner workings of the Demonstrator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● You should have had the chance to learn about how the profiles you’ve been sorted into have been created and how they are used to focus the “retrieval” being done to enable the generation of a policy brief ● You will have the chance to learn more about how OpenAI trained GPT based on a massive amount of sources in order to develop it’s language prediction capacities ● You can learn about what that Retrieval-Augmented Generation is and how it is working - to the extent we can explain it. ● And, you can discover more about the sources that were used to train the Digital Democracy Demonstrator to grant it the “perspective” (and potentially limitations) it has. <p>(3) As such, we encourage you to take 15 minutes in pairs to explore the inner workings and behind the scenes elements of the Demonstrator and to discuss how you feel about these inner workings</p> <p>(a) As you watch the videos and review the source list, consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) How might each of these elements (RAG, how GPT was trained, the sources we used or didn’t use, how the profiles were created and how you were sorted) 	
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				<p>might benefit the outcomes that are produced or cause limitations?</p> <p>(ii) Does it cause any concern or relief when you know how many of these mechanisms of this AI system were shaped by human decisions?</p>	
			15 minutes	<p>Participants watch a projection of the videos which explore the AI Metabolism of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator.</p> <p>The DDD allows participants to watch 3 explainer-videos and to review the data sources which the DDD relies upon.</p> <p>In pairs, the participants can discuss how what they've learned affects their perspective / assumptions about the Digital Democracy Demonstrator.</p>	
			20 minutes	<p>Once participants have had a chance to explore the metabolism, [Name Facilitator(s)] facilitate a conversation amongst the participants. The purpose of this discussion is to prompt critical reflection amongst the participants about what they've just learned, how it's informed their understanding of how the DDD works, and what their hesitations / critiques are.</p> <p>Consider using some of the following prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Whether the data is representative of all relevant experiences and view points?</i> • <i>What kind of biases may have informed the selection of data, creation of profiles, and use of particular parameters / instructions to guide the GPT?</i> • <i>How do the "black boxes" - how OpenAI trained ChatGPT to begin with and how RAG system works - affect your understanding and levels of trust in GPT's capability to produce usable outputs?</i> 	
11:30	Break		10 minutes		

11:40	Generating an Initial Policy Brief	Participant Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboratively draft a prompt to use for GPT • Select which source (Newspaper articles, Policy Papers, academic journals, or a mix of all three) to request GPT rely on. • Witness the automated generation of a policy brief based on prompt, selected source, and “user profile” distribution in the room. 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] facilitates a process amongst participants to draft a singular prompt they can input into the specialty GPT.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propose EU Labour market policy solutions, citing the relevant sources you rely upon. Please keep in mind that mistakes erode my trust, so be accurate and thorough. • Generate a policy brief on the topic of AI and the EU Labour market. Focus on proposing policies that address concerns across the spectrum of technology, societal, and economic perspectives. • "Task: Create a comprehensive EU policy brief on AI and labour." • Role: You are a neutral policy advisor to the European Commission. Task: Evaluate AI's impact on EU labour markets. Constraints: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use only sources from selected list/s • ... 	Projector Printer Red pens
			5 minutes	<p>Using a single laptop, which is connected to a projector, [Name Facilitator(s)] inputs the prompt into the GPT so all participants can observe the automated generation of a policy brief.</p> <p>[Name Facilitator(s)] prints enough copies of the brief for each participant to have one copy.</p>	
12:00	Lunch		60m		Facilitators meet to reflect on how morning has gone and to integrate any changes based on learnings from the morning.

13:00	Policy Brief Review #1	Participant Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Critically review 2-pager generated by specialty GPT ● Fracture implicit trust or apathy toward AI ● Critically reflect on ways to improve demonstrator prompt ● Adjust prompt to reflect discussions 	3 minutes	<p>--- introduces the next exercise: a review and revision of the current policy brief.</p> <p>--- distributes a copy of the brief and a red pen to each of the participants.</p>	
			15 minutes	<p>Each participant takes 15 minutes to review and redline the first draft of the policy paper.</p> <p>3 lenses for review:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What specific claims or recommendations in the policy brief stand out to you, and how do they align with your understanding of current EU labour issues? 2. Can you identify any potential biases or gaps in the policy brief? Consider which perspectives or stakeholders might be underrepresented or overlooked. 3. How trustworthy do you find this AI-generated brief? What elements contribute to or detract from its credibility, and what additional information or sources would you need to verify its content? 	
			15 minutes	<p>Once all participants have finished their review and redline, --- bring all the participants together in a circular space to consider their reflections as they make decisions about how to change their next use of the GPT, i.e., do they want to alter the prompt (if relevant), manually alter the distribution of profiles, reliance on a different source/s, etc.</p> <p>Script: <i>Thank you for taking the time to so thoroughly review and propose edits on this initial policy brief. We will dive deeper into your reflections soon, but, in the meantime, we'd like to run this process one more time to see how differences in the prompt, source/s, or parameters affect the output. So, hold on to your notes, but let's discuss what we could change about what (and how) we ask</i></p>	

				<p><i>the specialty GPT to see if we can produce something closer to our intentions. So, first, let's hear from folks.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. What were your main concerns or surprises when reviewing the AI-generated policy brief, and how might these insights inform future use of AI in policy-making?</i> <i>2. Based on your individual reviews, what specific improvements would you suggest for the AI prompt to generate a more comprehensive and balanced policy brief in the next iteration?</i> <i>3. How do you think the use of AI-generated policy briefs could impact the democratic process in shaping EU Labour Policy? Consider both potential benefits and risks.</i> <i>4. Reflecting on this experience, what role do you believe citizens should play in overseeing and guiding the development of AI systems used in democratic decision-making?</i> <p>Once there is agreement about the ways participants would like to alter the mechanisms of the specialty GPT, --- inputs the prompt into the GPT (using the projector) so all participants can observe the automated generation of a policy brief.</p> <p>--- prints enough copies of the brief for each participant to have one copy.</p>	
13:33	Policy Brief Review #2	Participant Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critically review 2-pager generated by specialty GPT Fracture implicit trust or apathy 	3 minutes	<p>--- introduces the next exercise: a review and revision of the second draft of the policy brief.</p> <p>--- distributes a copy of the brief and a red pen to each of the participants.</p>	
			10 minutes	<p>Each participant takes xx minutes to review and redline the first draft of the policy paper.</p> <p>3 lenses for review:</p>	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> toward AI ● Critically reflect on ways to improve demonstrator prompt ● Collaboratively adjust prompt to reflect discussions ● Understand how prompt engineering changes the output 		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What specific claims or recommendations in the policy brief stand out to you, and how do they align with your understanding of current EU labour issues? 2. Can you identify any potential biases or gaps in the policy brief? Consider which perspectives or stakeholders might be underrepresented or overlooked. 3. How trustworthy do you find this AI-generated brief? What elements contribute to or detract from its credibility, and what additional information or sources would you need to verify its content? 	
			15 minutes	<p>Once all participants have finished their review and redline, --- bring all the participants together in a circular space to consider their reflections as they make decisions about how to change their next use of the GPT, i.e., do they want to alter the prompt (if relevant), manually alter the distribution of profiles, reliance on a different source/s, etc.</p> <p>Script: <i>Thank you for taking the time to so thoroughly review and propose edits on this initial policy brief. We will dive deeper into your reflections soon, but, in the meantime, we'd like to run this process one more time to see how differences in the prompt, source/s, or parameters affect the output. So, hold on to your notes, but let's discuss what we could change about what (and how) we ask the specialty GPT to see if we can produce something closer to our intentions. So, first, let's hear from folks.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>How does the second version of the policy brief compare to the first? What specific improvements or changes do you notice, and how do they address the concerns raised in our previous discussion?</i> 2. <i>In what ways has the revised AI prompt influenced the content and quality of the second draft? Are there any unexpected outcomes or</i> 	

				<p><i>new issues that have emerged?</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. <i>Considering the iterative process we've just experienced, what potential do you see for AI-assisted policy brief generation in real-world policy-making? What safeguards or processes might be necessary?</i> 4. <i>How has this exercise affected your views on the role of AI in democracy? Do you feel more or less confident about the use of AI in policy-making processes after seeing the improvement between drafts?</i> 5. <i>Based on this experience, what recommendations would you make to policymakers or AI developers about the development and use of AI systems for generating policy briefs or other democratic decision-making tools?</i> 	
14:00	Break		10 minutes		
14:10	Process reflections and discussion	<p>Participant Experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● General reflection on experience in Lab ● Discuss overall experience in the digital democracy lab and the trustworthiness of platform and process ● Provide 	40 minutes	<p>Once all participants have returned from their break, --- and --- bring all the participants together in a circular space to discuss their reflections.</p> <p>--- and --- can use the following questions to surface relevant insights. --- and --- can select and adapt these questions based on the specific context of their workshop, the time available for discussion, and the particular areas they want to explore more deeply. They may also want to encourage participants to generate their own questions during the reflection process.</p> <p>Optional questions to select from for discussion:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Process Evaluation: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. In what ways did the AI-enabled process enhance or hinder the policy creation process compared to what you know about 	<p>We can consider dividing this process into:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Smaller group reflections and then a plenary discussion 2. A world cafe 3. An independent, creative reflection exercise

		<p>facilitators and organisers with insight into (1) integrating/relying on AI which should be shared as outputs from KT4D project and (2) how the digital democracy lab should be adapted to improve efficacy of experience.</p>	<p>traditional methods?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Trust & Legitimacy: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Does the use of AI in this process increase or decrease the legitimacy and trustworthiness of the resulting policy brief in your eyes? Why? 3. Affordances & Limitations: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What unique benefits or insights did the AI-enabled process provide that might be difficult to achieve through traditional policy-making methods? b. What limitations or drawbacks did you observe in using AI for this task? 4. Potential Improvements: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What other kinds of “<i>mindful friction</i>” points or “<i>contestable loops</i>” could be incorporated into the Digital Democracy Demonstrator and/or Digital Democracy lab to make the process and outputs generated by an AI more legitimate and trustworthy: 5. Broader Implications: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What potential risks or ethical concerns do you foresee if this approach were to be widely adopted? b. How might this process change the role of citizens, experts, and policymakers in shaping policy? c. What skills or knowledge do you think citizens would need to effectively engage in AI-enabled policy processes like this? 6. Personal Reflections: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. How did participating in this process change your views on the role of AI in democracy and policymaking? 7. Future Directions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. How might this process need to be adapted for different cultural or political contexts? 	<p>“Contestable loops”:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interactive control: Humans can intervene in the AI's prediction-to-decision process by providing additional information. ● Post-decision contestation: This includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Explanations of how and why decisions were made ● Channels for affected individuals to voice objections ● Arenas for debate between system representatives and those contesting
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					<p>decisions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An obligation for system operators to respond to objections and potentially reverse or repair decisions
14:50	Closing Out	<p>Participant Experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depart having enhanced critical digital literacy 	10 minutes	--- and --- offer closing remarks and wrap up the Digital Democracy Lab	

Appendix E: Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Madrid

Digital Democracy Lab | Democratic Stewardship of AI Enabled Democratic Decisions

Facilitation Guide | Use Case 2 & 3

Dates: Friday, 25 October, 2024 (Krakow) | Tuesday, 29 October, 2024 (Madrid)

Place:

Duration: 5 hours (4 hours + 1 hour lunch)

Target Audience: Citizens and CSOs

Workshop Objectives:

- **Develop critical digital literacy:** Enhance participants' understanding of AI systems used in democratic deliberation and policy-making contexts, including exploring the "metabolism" of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator and AI systems more generally.
- **Practise democratic stewardship:** Provide hands-on experience in generating, reviewing, and revising AI-produced materials, demonstrating the concept of democracy-in-the-loop and democratic stewardship of technology.
- **Evaluate AI in democracy:** Encourage reflection on the trustworthiness, legitimacy, and potential impacts of using AI in democratic and policy-making processes, including discussion of risks, benefits, and ethical considerations.

- **Identify improvements and implications:** Explore potential enhancements, limitations, and broader implications of AI-enabled democratic deliberation and policy creation processes.
- **Gather insights for future development:** Collect participant feedback on their experience with the AI system and overall process to inform future iterations of the Digital Democracy Lab and contribute to the broader KT4D project.

Value Proposition:

The Digital Democracy Lab offers you a hands-on opportunity to explore the intersection of AI and democratic decision-making. In this 5-hour workshop (including a 1-hour lunch), you'll:

1. Develop critical digital literacy by examining the inner-workings and design decisions of AI systems, generally, and AI systems used in democratic deliberation and policy-making, more specifically.
2. Gain practical experience in democratic stewardship of technology by generating, reviewing, and revising AI-produced policy briefs.
3. Evaluate the trustworthiness and legitimacy of AI in democratic processes through direct interaction with a specialised AI system.
4. Contribute to improving AI-enabled democratic deliberation by providing feedback on your experience and identifying potential enhancements.
5. Engage in meaningful discussions about the ethical considerations, risks, and benefits of integrating AI into policy-making.
6. Enhance your ability to participate in future public debates on AI governance by understanding both its potential and limitations.

By participating, you'll play an active role in shaping how AI could be responsibly integrated into democratic processes - and how democratic stewardship can be integrated into new technologies -, ensuring that future implementations align with citizens' values and expectations.

DIGITAL DEMOCRACY LAB - USE CASE 2 & 3					
Time	Activity	Goal/s	Duration	Structure + Notes + Facilitator(s)	Technical Notes
	Set Up	To ensure we are adequately prepared and materials are organised for an optimal participant experience.	60-90 minutes	<i>[Name Facilitator(s)] arrive at site to set up and ensure everything is in place.</i> -----	<input type="checkbox"/> Tablets / laptops / stationary computers are set up and have the Digital Democracy Demonstrator loaded <input type="checkbox"/> Projector is set up <input type="checkbox"/> Printer is linked, set up, and full of paper <input type="checkbox"/> Red pens and other workshop tools are compiled <input type="checkbox"/> Chairs are grouped in a circular shape for initial plenary
10:00	Gather and welcome	Participant Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcomed to the lab • Introduce themselves to each other + complete check in questions • Receive an overview of day's agenda 	10 minutes	<i>[Name Facilitator(s)]</i> introduces themselves and <i>- [Name Facilitator(s)]</i> . Together, they invite all participants to introduce themselves and respond to the check in question/ playful self-assessment of critical digital literacy. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fill in the blanks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ I trust AI to help me with _____ because _____ ○ I don't trust AI to help me with _____ because _____ 	
			5 minutes	<i>[Name Facilitator(s)]</i> offers a formal welcome and some short introductory statements. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to include a framing which situates participants within an 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Become intellectually prepared to begin tasks of Lab</i> 		<p>“imaginary” use case, in which their local municipality is considering using the Digital Democracy Lab to make specific policy decisions. In this case, the municipality is exploring policy related to Labour Policy and AI. So, we are asking participants to engage in the Lab from this perspective, so we can explore not whether this technology and/or forum is “good” or “bad”, but to explore the ways by which a technology such as this and a forum which affords democratic stewardship can affect democratic decision making processes and afford effective and helpful democracy-in-the-loop technologies.</p>	
			10 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] provides an accessible introduction about intersections of democracy and AI.</p>	
			5 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] provides participants with a briefing about the primary set of tasks they will conduct as part of the Digital Democracy Lab:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To critically engage with - and democratically steward - an AI supported process for creating and revising speculative EU Labor policy. • While we will use EU Labour Policy and the integration of AI as a focal point for our conversation, we just want to emphasise that the real purpose of our Lab is for us to experience, and as we said, critically engage and explore how we can democratically steward an AI in this process. 	
10:30	Profile Quiz	<p>Participant Experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Understand the purpose and value of providing their positionality regarding AI, Economy, and current system/s</i> 	5 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] introduces the quiz which participants will take.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The following 30-question quiz explores your views on technology, societal systems, and economic priorities. It covers topics from automation to wealth redistribution. Your answers will help gauge which policy positions you might support or oppose, providing insights into your perspective on key modern issues alongside other participants. • Answer each question based on your genuine beliefs, not what you think is “correct” or socially acceptable. There are no right or wrong responses. You’ll be placed into one of eight personas representing 	<p>The quiz</p> <p>Facilitators need to “Create the session” and complete the quiz themselves in order for the process to work. Participants should “join the session”.</p>

		<p>structures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand and - to the extent possible enjoy - the process of responding to quiz questions and sharing positionality. • Provide facilitators insight the particular positionality they have 		<p>different views on technology, society, and economics. The Demonstrator will then generate a policy brief aligned with all participants' perspectives.”</p>	
			15 minutes	<p>Each participant - using a provided tablet, laptop, or their own phone - completes the initial profile quiz on the Digital Democracy Demonstrator.</p> <p>Once all participants have completed the quiz, [Name Facilitator(s)] introduces the next steps</p>	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] should move from participant to participant to ensure they are following the processes and understand how to complete the quiz.</p>
10:50	Understand the AI Metabolism / Recipe	<p>Participant Experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore the data used to train the specialty GPT - how it was selected, and by whom • Learn how data was synthesised - using RAG (Retrieval-augmented generation) • Understand the parameters (instructions) used to train 	5 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] clarifies (1) the use of the quiz results, (2) provides an orientation to participants for how to navigate the opportunity to understand the AI’s metabolism / recipe for producing the output they will engage with later in the workshop, and (3) encourages participants to explore the metabolism in an in-depth way.</p> <p>(1) Your results on the Digital Democracy Demonstrator are not necessarily indicative of your entire perspective regarding technology, societal systems, and economic priorities; But, it does offer some insight into the kinds of ideas, opportunities, or policies you might find most exciting.. or concerning. The way the Digital Democracy Demonstrator works is that it will consider your profile and the other profiles in the room. It will consider these profiles as lenses as it uses an automated approach called Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to sort through source materials from newspapers across Europe, academic papers, and policy papers on the topics of AI and labour policy to generate a policy brief - i.e., a proposal for the kind of policy the EU should enact</p>	

		<p>model and how they were created, and by whom, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How the profiles were created, by whom, and how profiles were used to train GPT ● Understand the limitations and biases of parameters, profiles, and data selected, created, and relied up 		<p>on the topic.</p> <p>The policy brief that the Demonstrator will generate will pull together cited sentences or sections from across all the sources which - based on how the Demonstrator’s parameters were set - it calculates should align most effectively with the values and expectations of each of you - i.e., the different profiles - in the room.</p> <p>(2) In order to help you understand how all of this happening and offer you more opportunity to critically engage with the Demonstrator system, you will now take some time to explore the inner workings of the Demonstrator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● You should have had the chance to learn about how the profiles you’ve been sorted into have been created and how they are used to focus the “retrieval” being done to enable the generation of a policy brief ● You will have the chance to learn more about how OpenAI trained GPT based on a massive amount of sources in order to develop it’s language prediction capacities ● You can learn about what that Retrieval-Augmented Generation is and how it is working - to the extent we can explain it. ● And, you can discover more about the sources that were used to train the Digital Democracy Demonstrator to grant it the “perspective” (and potentially limitations) it has. <p>(3) As such, we encourage you to take 15 minutes in pairs to explore the inner workings and behind the scenes elements of the Demonstrator and to discuss how you feel about these inner workings</p> <p>(a) As you watch the videos and review the source list, consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) How might each of these elements (RAG, how GPT was trained, the sources we used or didn’t use, how the profiles were created and how you were sorted) 	
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				<p>might benefit the outcomes that are produced or cause limitations?</p> <p>(ii) Does it cause any concern or relief when you know how many of these mechanisms of this AI system were shaped by human decisions?</p>	
			15 minutes	<p>Participants watch a projection of the videos which explore the AI Metabolism of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator.</p> <p>The DDD allows participants to watch 3 explainer-videos and to review the data sources which the DDD relies upon.</p> <p>In pairs, the participants can discuss how what they've learned affects their perspective / assumptions about the Digital Democracy Demonstrator.</p>	
			20 minutes	<p>Once participants have had a chance to explore the metabolism, [Name Facilitator(s)] facilitate a conversation amongst the participants. The purpose of this discussion is to prompt critical reflection amongst the participants about what they've just learned, how it's informed their understanding of how the DDD works, and what their hesitations / critiques are.</p> <p>Consider using some of the following prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Whether the data is representative of all relevant experiences and view points?</i> • <i>What kind of biases may have informed the selection of data, creation of profiles, and use of particular parameters / instructions to guide the GPT?</i> • <i>How do the "black boxes" - how OpenAI trained ChatGPT to begin with and how RAG system works - affect your understanding and levels of trust in GPT's capability to produce usable outputs?</i> 	
11:30	Break		10 minutes		

11:40	Generating an Initial Policy Brief	Participant Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboratively draft a prompt to use for GPT • Select which source (Newspaper articles, Policy Papers, academic journals, or a mix of all three) to request GPT rely on. • Witness the automated generation of a policy brief based on prompt, selected source, and “user profile” distribution in the room. 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] facilitates a process amongst participants to draft a singular prompt they can input into the specialty GPT.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propose EU Labour market policy solutions, citing the relevant sources you rely upon. Please keep in mind that mistakes erode my trust, so be accurate and thorough. • Generate a policy brief on the topic of AI and the EU Labour market. Focus on proposing policies that address concerns across the spectrum of technology, societal, and economic perspectives. • "Task: Create a comprehensive EU policy brief on AI and labour." • Role: You are a neutral policy advisor to the European Commission. Task: Evaluate AI's impact on EU labour markets. Constraints: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use only sources from selected list/s • ... 	Projector Printer Red pens
			5 minutes	<p>Using a single laptop, which is connected to a projector, [Name Facilitator(s)] inputs the prompt into the GPT so all participants can observe the automated generation of a policy brief.</p> <p>[Name Facilitator(s)] prints enough copies of the brief for each participant to have one copy.</p>	
12:00	Lunch		60m		Facilitators meet to reflect on how morning has gone and to integrate any changes based on learnings from the morning.

13:00	Policy Brief Review #1	Participant Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Critically review 2-pager generated by specialty GPT ● Fracture implicit trust or apathy toward AI ● Critically reflect on ways to improve demonstrator prompt ● Adjust prompt to reflect discussions 	3 minutes	<p>--- introduces the next exercise: a review and revision of the current policy brief.</p> <p>--- distributes a copy of the brief and a red pen to each of the participants.</p>	
			15 minutes	<p>Each participant takes 15 minutes to review and redline the first draft of the policy paper.</p> <p>3 lenses for review:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What specific claims or recommendations in the policy brief stand out to you, and how do they align with your understanding of current EU labour issues? 2. Can you identify any potential biases or gaps in the policy brief? Consider which perspectives or stakeholders might be underrepresented or overlooked. 3. How trustworthy do you find this AI-generated brief? What elements contribute to or detract from its credibility, and what additional information or sources would you need to verify its content? 	
			15 minutes	<p>Once all participants have finished their review and redline, --- bring all the participants together in a circular space to consider their reflections as they make decisions about how to change their next use of the GPT, i.e., do they want to alter the prompt (if relevant), manually alter the distribution of profiles, reliance on a different source/s, etc.</p> <p>Script: <i>Thank you for taking the time to so thoroughly review and propose edits on this initial policy brief. We will dive deeper into your reflections soon, but, in the meantime, we'd like to run this process one more time to see how differences in the prompt, source/s, or parameters affect the output. So, hold on to your notes, but let's discuss what we could change about what (and how) we ask</i></p>	

				<p><i>the specialty GPT to see if we can produce something closer to our intentions. So, first, let's hear from folks.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. What were your main concerns or surprises when reviewing the AI-generated policy brief, and how might these insights inform future use of AI in policy-making?</i> <i>2. Based on your individual reviews, what specific improvements would you suggest for the AI prompt to generate a more comprehensive and balanced policy brief in the next iteration?</i> <i>3. How do you think the use of AI-generated policy briefs could impact the democratic process in shaping EU Labour Policy? Consider both potential benefits and risks.</i> <i>4. Reflecting on this experience, what role do you believe citizens should play in overseeing and guiding the development of AI systems used in democratic decision-making?</i> <p>Once there is agreement about the ways participants would like to alter the mechanisms of the specialty GPT, --- inputs the prompt into the GPT (using the projector) so all participants can observe the automated generation of a policy brief.</p> <p>--- prints enough copies of the brief for each participant to have one copy.</p>	
13:33	Policy Brief Review #2	Participant Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critically review 2-pager generated by specialty GPT Fracture implicit trust or apathy 	3 minutes	<p>--- introduces the next exercise: a review and revision of the second draft of the policy brief.</p> <p>--- distributes a copy of the brief and a red pen to each of the participants.</p>	
			10 minutes	<p>Each participant takes xx minutes to review and redline the first draft of the policy paper.</p> <p>3 lenses for review:</p>	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> toward AI ● Critically reflect on ways to improve demonstrator prompt ● Collaboratively adjust prompt to reflect discussions ● Understand how prompt engineering changes the output 		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What specific claims or recommendations in the policy brief stand out to you, and how do they align with your understanding of current EU labour issues? 2. Can you identify any potential biases or gaps in the policy brief? Consider which perspectives or stakeholders might be underrepresented or overlooked. 3. How trustworthy do you find this AI-generated brief? What elements contribute to or detract from its credibility, and what additional information or sources would you need to verify its content? 	
			15 minutes	<p>Once all participants have finished their review and redline, --- bring all the participants together in a circular space to consider their reflections as they make decisions about how to change their next use of the GPT, i.e., do they want to alter the prompt (if relevant), manually alter the distribution of profiles, reliance on a different source/s, etc.</p> <p>Script: <i>Thank you for taking the time to so thoroughly review and propose edits on this initial policy brief. We will dive deeper into your reflections soon, but, in the meantime, we'd like to run this process one more time to see how differences in the prompt, source/s, or parameters affect the output. So, hold on to your notes, but let's discuss what we could change about what (and how) we ask the specialty GPT to see if we can produce something closer to our intentions. So, first, let's hear from folks.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>How does the second version of the policy brief compare to the first? What specific improvements or changes do you notice, and how do they address the concerns raised in our previous discussion?</i> 2. <i>In what ways has the revised AI prompt influenced the content and quality of the second draft? Are there any unexpected outcomes or</i> 	

				<p><i>new issues that have emerged?</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. <i>Considering the iterative process we've just experienced, what potential do you see for AI-assisted policy brief generation in real-world policy-making? What safeguards or processes might be necessary?</i> 4. <i>How has this exercise affected your views on the role of AI in democracy? Do you feel more or less confident about the use of AI in policy-making processes after seeing the improvement between drafts?</i> 5. <i>Based on this experience, what recommendations would you make to policymakers or AI developers about the development and use of AI systems for generating policy briefs or other democratic decision-making tools?</i> 	
14:00	Break		10 minutes		
14:10	Process reflections and discussion	<p>Participant Experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● General reflection on experience in Lab ● Discuss overall experience in the digital democracy lab and the trustworthiness of platform and process ● Provide 	40 minutes	<p>Once all participants have returned from their break, --- and --- bring all the participants together in a circular space to discuss their reflections.</p> <p>--- and --- can use the following questions to surface relevant insights. --- and --- can select and adapt these questions based on the specific context of their workshop, the time available for discussion, and the particular areas they want to explore more deeply. They may also want to encourage participants to generate their own questions during the reflection process.</p> <p>Optional questions to select from for discussion:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Process Evaluation: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. In what ways did the AI-enabled process enhance or hinder the policy creation process compared to what you know about 	<p>We can consider dividing this process into:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Smaller group reflections and then a plenary discussion 2. A world cafe 3. An independent, creative reflection exercise

		<p>facilitators and organisers with insight into (1) integrating/relying on AI which should be shared as outputs from KT4D project and (2) how the digital democracy lab should be adapted to improve efficacy of experience.</p>	<p>traditional methods?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Trust & Legitimacy: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Does the use of AI in this process increase or decrease the legitimacy and trustworthiness of the resulting policy brief in your eyes? Why? 3. Affordances & Limitations: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What unique benefits or insights did the AI-enabled process provide that might be difficult to achieve through traditional policy-making methods? b. What limitations or drawbacks did you observe in using AI for this task? 4. Potential Improvements: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What other kinds of “<i>mindful friction</i>” points or “<i>contestable loops</i>” could be incorporated into the Digital Democracy Demonstrator and/or Digital Democracy lab to make the process and outputs generated by an AI more legitimate and trustworthy: 5. Broader Implications: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What potential risks or ethical concerns do you foresee if this approach were to be widely adopted? b. How might this process change the role of citizens, experts, and policymakers in shaping policy? c. What skills or knowledge do you think citizens would need to effectively engage in AI-enabled policy processes like this? 6. Personal Reflections: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. How did participating in this process change your views on the role of AI in democracy and policymaking? 7. Future Directions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. How might this process need to be adapted for different cultural or political contexts? 	<p>“Contestable loops”:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interactive control: Humans can intervene in the AI's prediction-to-decision process by providing additional information. ● Post-decision contestation: This includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Explanations of how and why decisions were made ● Channels for affected individuals to voice objections ● Arenas for debate between system representatives and those contesting
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					<p>decisions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An obligation for system operators to respond to objections and potentially reverse or repair decisions
14:50	Closing Out	<p>Participant Experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depart having enhanced critical digital literacy 	10 minutes	--- and --- offer closing remarks and wrap up the Digital Democracy Lab	

Appendix F: Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Dublin

Digital Democracy Lab | Integrating Meaningful Frictions for Democratic Stewardship

Facilitation Guide | Use Case 4

Date: 18:00, Wednesday, 13 November, 2024

Place: Bay 1, The Digital Hub, Beta Festival (Exact location TBD)

Duration: 2.5 hours (18:00 - 20:30)

Target Audience: Software engineers, developers, tech industry professionals, and researchers

Workshop Objectives:

- Explore the Digital Democracy Demonstrator (DDD) from a technical perspective
- Understand the concept of "meaningful/Trustworthy frictions" and their role in democratic stewardship of AI, and Democracy-in-the-loop technologies, more generally
- Identify opportunities to integrate these frictions into the DDD
- Engage in hands-on activities to propose and prototype friction implementations

Value Proposition:

The Digital Democracy Lab offers you a unique 2.5-hour workshop to explore and shape the integration of AI in democratic processes and democratic stewardship in AI:

1. Gain hands-on experience with the Digital Democracy Demonstrator (DDD), including ~~potential~~ backend access, to understand its architecture and features.
 - a. [Digital Democracy Demonstrator Profiles and Profile Quiz](#)
 - b. Resources:
 - i. [List of resources that the Demonstrator was trained on](#)
 - ii. [Initial logic for resource selection](#)
2. Deepen your understanding of "meaningful/trustworthy frictions" and their role in ensuring democratic stewardship of AI systems.
3. Engage in a creative challenge to design and prototype 2-3 meaningful frictions for specific areas of the DDD, pushing the boundaries of human-AI collaboration in a governance context.
4. Collaborate with peers to tackle the complex balance between system efficiency, trustworthiness, and democratic values in AI.
5. Contribute directly to improving AI-enabled democratic deliberation by proposing innovative friction implementations.
6. Gain insights into the societal implications of AI in democratic processes, helping you create more responsible and democratically compatible AI technologies.

By participating, you'll have the opportunity to influence the development of best practices for integrating AI into democratic decision-making and democratic stewardship in AI, potentially shaping future standards in ethical AI development. This workshop offers a stimulating environment to apply your technical skills to critical questions of AI governance and democratic stewardship.

PRIMARY FACILITATORS

SUPPORTIVE FACILITATORS

TECHNICAL SUPPORT

DIGITAL DEMOCRACY LAB - USE CASE 4					
Time	Activity	Goal/s	Duration	Structure + Notes + Facilitator(s)	Technical Notes
17:00	Set Up Location: Bay 1, The Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To ensure we are adequately prepared and materials are organised for an optimal participant experience. 	45 minutes	<p><i>[Name Facilitator(s)] arrive at the site to set up and ensure everything is in place.</i></p> <p>-----</p> <p>Materials Needed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Laptops/devices with access to the DDD (ideally including backend access if possible) <input type="checkbox"/> Wifi passwords for the Digital Hub for laptops <input type="checkbox"/> Whiteboard or digital collaboration tool for brainstorming <input type="checkbox"/> Prototyping materials (could be digital tools or even just paper and markers for lo-fi prototyping) <input type="checkbox"/> Handouts with overview of meaningful frictions and democratic stewardship concepts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up a sandbox environment of the DDD for participants to experiment with Prepare clear documentation of the DDD's current architecture and features Develop a list of potential areas in the DDD where frictions could be integrated, in case participants need inspiration
17:45	Pizza (and participants) arrive Location: The Ethics Studio, The Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome participants as they arrive and encourage them to have something to eat before we start. 	15 minutes	<p><i>[Name Facilitator(s)] welcome participants and encourage them to grab pizza and a seat.</i></p> <p>-----</p>	

18:00	Welcome and introduction Location from here: Bay 1, The Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brief welcome and introductions Overview of KT4D, Digital Democracy Lab objectives and the DDD's purpose 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] offers a formal welcome, introductory statements, the agenda for the day, and facilitates a quick introductory exercise with the participants.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction Exercise: Quick standing spectrogram exercise: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> We ask participants to stand closer to one wall if they believe Integrating AI will make Democracy more effective and closer to the other wall if they believe Integrating Democracy will make AI more effective and somewhere in between the two walls, depending on their feelings. We then ask everyone to say their name and where they work / what perspective their bringing to this workshop We then select 1-2 people from each end of the spectrum and 1-2 from the middle to share their rationale for where they are standing. 	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)]</p> <p>*include where toilets are; fire exits and wifi code</p>
18:10	Understanding Democracy and the value of Meaningful Frictions in AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mini-lecture on meaningful/ trustworthy frictions and democratic stewardship Examples of frictions in existing technologies and their impacts 	15 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] provides an accessible and compelling introduction about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Democratic Exchange and innovation Role of technology in Democratic Exchange and Innovation Intentions of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator and Lab (as it relates to experimenting with the roles, affects, and affordances of technology and democratic exchange and innovation) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Present our intentions with the lab and the realities of how it played out in each use case with attention for the intentional (and unintentional) frictions and the meaningful (or distracting) impacts they had <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The role of democratically productive contestation loops and deliberation loops, which seemingly afforded democratic stewardship The use of meaningful / trustworthy frictions to enable, enhance, and generally afford a level of critical digital literacy while using technologies like AI Why (and where in the design and use of AI) democracy can/ought to 	<p>Style the “presentation” as a Socratic engagement, in which:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The presenter has some questions for the participants to answer (generally related to AI and Technology) The participants have each been given a question on a sheet of paper which they are meant to ask when cued

				play a role: Democracy-in-the-Loop Technologies	(generally related to democracy, contestation and deliberation loops, and meaningful frictions).
			10 minutes	[Name Facilitator(s)] responds to questions	
18:35	Hands-on Exploration of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guided tour of the DDD's features and backend Participants explore the system in pairs, noting areas where frictions could be integrated 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] offers a concise summary description of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator (DDD):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What the Demonstrator is, i.e., what it is meant to do; How it works; and Why it works that way based on the parameters and inputs that have been used to develop it. <p>Primary facilitator instructs the participants to split into trios and, together explore the front-end functionality and - to begin exploring - the backend code and design</p>	
			15 minutes	Participants - in trios- dive into the DDD.	Facilitators roam around the different pairs and collect initial observations from participants.
			5 minutes	<p>At 19:00, Primary facilitator warns the participants that they have 5 minutes remaining.</p> <p>At 19:04, Primary facilitator warns the participants that they have 1 minute remaining</p> <p>At 19:05, Primary facilitator thanks the groups and sends them to a 10 minute break</p>	

19:05	Break	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide participants with a chance to pause and mingle and for facilitators to get additional feedback 	10 minutes		<p>During this time, [Name Facilitator(s)] can convene to discuss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If any changes should be made for remainder of Lab; and • If any insights from the first hour should be incorporated into the next discussion. • Put posters on tables
19:15	Friction Integration Challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small groups of participants design and prototype 2-3 meaningful frictions • Groups of participants document their ideas 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] introduces the next group exercise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants will divide into groups of 3 • Each group self-selects a specific area of the Digital Democracy Demonstrator to focus on. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ This can be a specific moment in the interface or entire sub-components of the DDD experience • Using paper prototyping and/or playing in the DDD backend sandlot, groups work together to design and craft 1-3 minimum viable prototypes of meaningful / trustworthy frictions which can enhance or afford: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Critical digital literacy when using the AI system; 2. Contestation or deliberation amongst participants; or 3. Democratic effectiveness of the AI system. • Groups should document their ideas, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Opportunity for improvement ○ Description(s) of the friction(s) ○ Technical implementation approach ○ Expected impact on democratic stewardship, i.e., ability for 	<p>Participants are given posters</p> <p>Hack the system - how can we make it better for effective democracy?</p>

				participants to more effectively democratically dictate the values and expectations on which the AI system should operate	
			30 minutes	Participants - in groups of three - work together to define intervention opportunities and implementable frictions.	
			5 minutes	<p>At 19:55, Primary facilitator warns the participants that they have 5 minutes remaining and encourages them to identify what they collectively believe is their “best”, most impactful idea.</p> <p>At 19:59, Primary facilitator warns the participants that they have 1 minute remaining and encourages them to identify what they collectively believe is their “best”, most impactful idea.</p> <p>At 20:00, Primary facilitator thanks the groups and ask them to come back together</p>	
20:00	Group Shareback and Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Representative(s) from each group share their “best” idea Spurred by the ideas that have been shared, plenary engages in a broader discussion. 	25 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] facilitates a share back from each group. One representative from each group shares their group’s “best” idea. As part of this share back, the representative should indicate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How their group defined/understood what “best” meant within the context of selecting an idea. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How does it align with our intentions to encourage Democracy in the loop technologies and democratic stewardship of AI? What the opportunity area within the DDD is. What the idea is. What impact(s) - positive and, potentially, negative - their idea might have. <p>In the remaining time following the sharebacks - <i>assuming there is time</i> - Primary facilitator facilitates a short plenary discussion. The discussion can explore any/all the following topics, but [Name Facilitator(s)] should feel comfortable tying</p>	

				<p><i>the whole day together, in a way, with this conversation.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the challenges in implementing meaningful frictions which are easily overcome and which are more deeply entrenched? • In which ways could we - <i>a collective technologists 'we'</i> - more effectively design, develop, and/or deploy technologies, which balance efficiency with democratic values? • Where do you see potential applications of these concepts beyond the Digital Democracy Demonstrator? 	
20:10	Final Reflections and Next Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recap of key takeaways • Information on how insights will inform further research, policy, and technical developments and invitation to collaborate • Information on follow-up activities and opportunities for continued engagement 	10 minutes	<p>[Name Facilitator(s)] offers:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A closing synthesis of the day's discussions; 2. Information on what's to come with the KT4D project; and a 3. An invitation to stay involved in this work (KT4D, specifically, and Democratic stewardship of AI technologies, more generally). <p>If there is time, [Name Facilitator(s)] can ask to close the event with each participant sharing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>How has this workshop changed your perspective on AI in democratic processes?</i> 	

Design Considerations:

use case 4: everyone at the table will be mentally redesign the system. But they cant do what we do. We can show them why we chose to do this the way we did, because of the democratic principles that we are building into them.

Can you datafy democratic processes?

i was thinking that maybe for the use case in dublin we could, essentially, run a hackathon in which we frame it as a challenge for developers to identify opportunities within the AI system (DDD or otherwise) to integrate more effective meaningful frictions for democracy-in-the-loop stewardship of the AI's outcomes

basically i'm just trying to think of techy, playful exercises we can engage this group in that would be engaging and meaningful

It would be nice if we could set up a sandbox to play with the backend of the demonstrator

Flow:

- 1. Introduction about the necessity for and value of meaningful / trustworthy friction (in both technology and democracy alike)*
- 2. Brief Q&A*
- 3. "Playground" for software engineers to "hack" existing system and generate more precise and more effective frictions in the DDD.*
- 4. Discussion*

Appendix F: Facilitation Guide for Use Case in Dublin

A service blueprint is a diagram that visualizes the relationships between different service components — people, props (physical or digital evidence), and processes — that are directly tied to touchpoints in a specific participant journey.

SERVICE BLUEPRINT | Digital Democracy Lab

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

[@kt4democracy.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/org/kt4democracy)

[KT4Democracy](https://www.linkedin.com/company/kt4democracy)

Funded by
the European Union